

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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INTRODUCTION

The Market Assessment deliverable aims to present a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the RECAP market. To this end the first chapter analytically presents the profiles of all EU countries paying agencies, a brief market analysis on agricultural consultants and EU wide data for farmers and their collective entities.

In chapter two follows an analysis on third parties such as the DGs for Environment and Growth, the European Court of Auditors, the European Environment Agency, the European Space Agency and the MARS Unit of the Joint Research Center.

Current and future policy in the EU is expected to influence RECAP's market and therefore the scope of chapter 3 is to discover the shape of things to come and policy changes until and post 2020.

Public Procurement processes are analysed in chapter 4 focusing on specific rules and country specificities in order to identify possibilities and barriers since a large proportion of the target market is within the public sector.

Chapter 5 focuses on ICT penetration in the different countries and with respect specifically to some of the Digital Economy and Society Index indicators.

RECAP product self-assessment as an early assessment tool is presented in chapter 6 while the market assessment concludes in chapter 7 by arguing on the completion of the deliverable i.e. the identification of future potential competitors and planning of the field research to be conducted next spring to one of the upcoming regular meetings of the paying agencies.

1. TARGET GROUPS

1.1 Paying Agencies profiles

Paying Agencies are established in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 1306/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulations (EC) 908/2014 and 907/2014.

Paying Agencies are departments or bodies in the Member States responsible for the management and control of expenditure of the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).

With the exception of payments, all other tasks may be delegated.

Member States have accredited as Paying Agencies departments or bodies which have an administrative organisation and a system of internal control which provide sufficient guarantees that payments are legally consistent and regular, and properly accounted for. However, where Paying Agencies have been established at a regional level, Member States have, in addition, either accredited a Paying Agency at a national level for aid schemes which, by their nature, are managed at a national level or have conferred the management of these schemes on their regional Paying Agencies.

● Austria

Agrarmarkt Austria (AMA) was established in 1992 and it is under the supervision of the Federal Minister for Agriculture and Forestry, Environment and Water Management. It is administered by a Management Board and it is organised in directorates responsible for market organisation, market information, on-the-spot control, legal services, finances, GIS & IT applications and CAP-payments. Three autonomous units also operate supporting management services.

Procurements are handled by the Financial Sector (Directorate I), but also the IT department is responsible for IT purchases, including the procurement of computer systems.

The Federal Government has established the Federal Procurement Agency (BBG, "Bundesbeschaffung GmbH" in 2001 by the Federal Procurement Agency Act ("BBGmbH-Gesetz")) to provide central procurement services to federal agencies and in particular to negotiate framework contracts and make them available to the agencies. Federal Institutions are obliged to order from these contracts - unless they are able to obtain the same product to better conditions. Other public sector organisations like universities, communities, states, state-owned organisations or health organisations may take advantage of BBG's contracts and services for a modest fee. Delivery and payment is done directly between supplier and requesting public body.

AMA also has a subsidiary organization Agrarmarkt Austria Marketing GesmbH responsible for organising marketing of agricultural products.

Additionally, Agrarmarkt Austria (AMA) operates the internet service portal eAMA which offers its customers the possibility to process applications, notifications, queries and other administrative processes directly from the farm. Given that requirements in agriculture are continually changing, AMA strives to be always up-to-

date with the latest technological and technical standards. New applications and functions are designed along with and for the user.

This type of modern communication in the agricultural sector is a major concern for the AMA. The diversity of applications of eAMA ranges from the RinderNET available for reporting and querying to the central cattle database, to the stable register, and to the spatial area application geographical information system. An electronic archive containing scanned applications and notifications, an overview of personal accounts and movements, as well as the optional possibility of electronic delivery of notifications are some of the services offered.

AMA is accredited for the implementation of a Quality Management System according to the international standard ISO 9001, an Environmental Management System according to ISO 14001 standard and the Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS) of the European Commission, an Information Security Management System ISO 27001 and an Information technology - Service Management System according to ISO 20000 standard.

CONTACT DETAILS

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Email : www.ama.at/Intro
Website : gap@ama.gv.at or <https://www.ama.at/Allgemein/Kontakt>

● BELGIUM

There are two Belgian Payment Agencies, one of the Flemish Government - Department of Agriculture and Fisheries and one of the Service Public of Wallonia – Department of Agriculture.

Flemish Government - Department of Agriculture and Fisheries

The Department of Agriculture and Fisheries of the Flemish public authority, together with the Flanders' Agricultural Marketing Board (VLAM), the Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research (ILVO) and the Strategic Advisory Council for Agriculture and Fisheries (SALV), make up the Agricultural and Fisheries Policy Area.

The Department of Agriculture and Fisheries deals with the development, implementation, control and evaluation of all matters in the field of agriculture, horticulture, fisheries and the countryside. The department works in close cooperation with the Minister of Agriculture.

The department is led by the Secretary General and consists of eleven divisions. The Division Secretariat-General consists of:

- the secretariat of the Secretary General
- the head of the Flemish Paying Agency

The Secretary General also presides the Management Committee, i.e. the body managing all entities of the Agricultural and Fisheries Policy Area.

The Flemish Agency has been the recognised body responsible for the management of European agricultural funds in Flanders. The agency insures proper registration of aid, payment and recognition applications, enables effective control on the strict compliance with the contracted aid conditions and ensures proper and timely payment of the aid, accounting and declaration to the European Commission.

The Flemish Paying Agency is organized in the Income Support Division, the Entrepreneurship and Development Department and the Department of Organizational and Financial Management and Communication (Flemish Rural Network). The management of some measures and some control aspects are delegated to the Flemish Land Agency (VLM) and the Agency for Nature and Forest (ANB). The Department of Organizational and Financial Management and Communications is responsible for the execution of all payments, accounting treatment and the internal audit function.

Service Public of Wallonia - Department of Agriculture

Paying Agency of Wallonia, for the EAGF and EAFRD funds is under the Directorate-General for Agriculture, Natural Resources and the Environment. The missions of the Paying Agency (OPW) are carried out by two departments: Department of Aids and Department of Agriculture. The position of Director of the OPW is hence assured by the agent who holds the post of Inspector General of the Department of European Policies and International Agreements of the Audit Unit for EAGF and EAFRD funds.

Department of Agriculture – DAGRI operates the functions for the payment and recording of EU regional or co-financed aid and subsidies and participates in the monitoring and maintenance of its authorization as a paying agency on behalf of the agricultural funds of the European Union.

External Directorates also reinforce the department that are established at Ath, Ciney, Huy, Libramont, Malmédy, Thuin, and Wavre.

Department of Aids – Dai provides support to the paying agency specifically by providing payment and accounting functions for aid and grants granted within the scope of the Directorate-General's powers (EU, regional or co-financed aid in agriculture and the environment) and contributes to the follow-up and maintenance of the authorization of the Paying Agency on behalf of the agricultural funds of the Union (EAGF, EAFRD).

Additionally the Directorate for the granting of agricultural aid of Dai assures the quality management and manages the necessary public contracts both for the Department of Aids and the Department of Agriculture.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Flemish Paying Agency, King Albert II, 35, bus 40-1030 Brussels
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Email : tim.ampe@lv.vlaanderen.be
Website : <http://lv.vlaanderen.be/nl/home/over-ons/vlaams-betaalorgaan>

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Service Public of Wallonia – DG03 – Department of Agriculture, Chaussée de Louvain 14, BE-5000 Namur
Telephone : +32 81 649 731
Email : Feedback.certificats.dgarne@spw.wallonie.be
Website : <http://agriculture.wallonie.be>

● BULGARIA

State Fund Agriculture – Paying Agency

The Fund operates in accordance with the national legislation and the applicable EU legislation (Decree No 151 of July 16, 2012 on the adoption of the Rules of Organization and Procedure of State Fund Agriculture). It is a legal entity with Headquarters in Sofia and it is a public institution operating with an off-budget account. The Fund's managing bodies are the Managing Board and the Executive Director.

It is organized in Headquarters and in 28 regional offices. The administration of the Headquarters is organized in 7 general administration Directorates and 10 specialized Administration Directorates, including financial control and IT, the Internal Audit Directorate, Administration and Control.

The Public Procurement Directorate is under the General Secretariat. It organizes and coordinates the procedures for awarding public contracts in accordance with the provisions of the Public Procurement Act (PPA).

The State Fund Agriculture – Paying Agency is accredited for the implementation of a Quality Management System and an Information Security Management System according to international standards ISO 9001 & ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

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Email : dfz@dfz.bg
Website : www.dfz.bg/en/about-sfa/legal-documents/

● CROATIA

The Paying Agency for Agriculture, Fisheries and Rural Development (PAAFRD) is managed by a Director and a Deputy Director. It is organized in 12 Departments supervised by assistant Directors and also operates 21

**PAYING AGENCY FOR AGRICULTURE,
FISHERIES AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT**

regional offices. The Ministry of Agriculture supports technical functions of the Agency. The Agency has also delegated functions to external technical experts and the Ministry of Finance.

The procurement process is carried out according to the national Guide for Public Procurement Process by the Department of Finances.

Out of other necessary systems, the Agency also runs the Farmer's Register, the ARKOD – system for the digital identification of land parcel, and accompanying registers (vineyard register, register of the primary producers of food, register of ecological producers), ISAP – centralized electronic database (for the simultaneous data entry with 25 PAAFRD locations in the Republic of Croatia) and AGRONET – the secure internet application through which the farmers are viewing data on their farm and are electronically filling in application requests for supports once a year.

PAAFRD has been accredited for the implementation of an Information Security Management System according to the international standard ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

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Email : info@apprrr.hr
Website : www.apprrr.hr

● CYPRUS

The Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation (CAPO) is an independent legal board that is not under any Ministry or Department of the Government. The Commissioner heads the Agency and is supported in his work by the Assistant Commissioner. In addition, within the responsibilities of CAPO is the management of all financial aid paid from national funds for supporting agriculture and rural areas.

The agency has three autonomous units (internal audit, public relations and combating fraud and legal issues) and eight departments that serve operational and administrative functions. The procurement process follows the procedure of public procurement tenders. Purchases are the responsibility of the Department of Administration and Human Resources in accordance to National Law on procurement procedure and Related Matters of 2016. N.73 (I) / 2016.

The Agency may delegate part or all of the payment approval responsibilities, as well as work

related to the technical services and the Integrated Administration and Control System. The delegation is made to other bodies such as Public or Private Bodies. The Commissioner assures that they have proper qualifications and available means. Currently CAPO maintains four (4) Delegation agreements and one (1) Cooperation agreement with the Ministries of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment, Energy, Trade, Industry and Tourism, Interior Affairs and the Ministry of Finance.

CAPO implements an Information Security Management System according to the international standard ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : 20 Michail Kostofta st (Esperidon and Kostofta), 2000 Nikosia, PO Box 16102, 2086 Nicosia
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Email : www.capo.gov.cy
Website : info@capo.gov.cy

● CZECH REPUBLIC

State Agricultural Intervention Fund is based in Prague and its activities are regulated by the State Agricultural Intervention Fund no. 256/2000 Coll., as amended by Acts no. 128/2003 Coll. and no. 85/2004 Coll., as well as implementing legislation in the form of Government Regulation. The State Agricultural Intervention Fund SZIF is a legal entity under the Ministry of Agriculture. SZIF is composed of a central department and seven regional units.

Operation and management of the Agency are controlled by the Supervisory Board. The chairman and another three members of the Board are elected by a vote among MPs. The Vice-Chairman is elected by a vote among Senators.

Procurements at SZIF are carried out in accordance with the Act No. 137/2006 on public procurement, while low-value public procurements are in accordance with the applicable SZIF internal regulation.

The Agency is accredited for the implementation of an Information Security Management System according to the international standard ISO 27001 (2004).

CONTACT DETAILS

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Website : www.szif.cz

● DENMARK

The Danish Agrifish Agency is an agency under the Ministry of Environment and Food. It is managed by an Executive Director and it is organized in four administrative departments ((Internal) Audit, Secretariat for the Executive Board Innovation and Project Organization & Relocation)) and four executing departments (Resources, Control & Fisheries, EU & Agriculture & Customers & Production).

Procurements are carried out according to the National Law on the enforcement of procurement rules, etc. in accordance to EU Regulations.

The Agency is operating a portal that allows its clients to directly access applications of field maps and plots, as well as access information and registries.

The Danish Agrifish Agency is accredited for the implementation of an Information Security Management System according to the international standard ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : The Danish AgriFish Agency, Nyropsgade 30, DK-1780 København V, Denmark
Telephone : +45 33 95 80 00
Email : mail@naturerhverv.dk
Website : <http://agrifish.dk/agriculture/>

● ESTONIA

Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board (ARIB) was established in summer 2000 as a government agency working in the area of administration of the Ministry of Rural Affairs on the basis of the Agricultural Registers and Information Centre.

The main pillars in ARIB's history have been the accreditation of ARIB as a SAPARD agency in June 2001 and its accreditation of ARIB as the European Union EAGGF payment agency in 2004.

The agency is organised in Management, Administrative and Financial Departments as well as Developmental departments. The main office is situated in Tartu and the rest 15 service-offices are placed in all seven Estonian counties.

e-PRIA is the client portal of the Agricultural Registers and Information Board, through which clients can submit documents to ARIB and check their details in ARIB's registers. The portal represents a convenient way for the Agency's clients to exchange information online. (<https://epria.pria.ee/epria/>).

No information on public procurements or ISO accreditation was available.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Tähe 4, Tartu 51010

Telephone : 737 1200

Email : pria@pria.ee

Website : www.pria.ee

● FINLAND

The Agency for Rural Affairs (Mavi) is the Finnish Paying Agency responsible for the use of funds of the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development in Finland.

The organisational structure of the Agency for Rural Affairs is based on processes for farmer support, project, enterprise as well as structural and market support. The three departments in the Agency for Rural Affairs are the Department of Agriculture, the Department of Rural

Development and the Market Department. IT systems are maintained and developed in cooperation with the National Land Survey of Finland. The three units supporting all departments are Financial Management, Information and Technology Services and Administrative Services. In addition, Internal Audit, the Quality Assurance Unit and Communications report directly to the Director-General. The Director-General is the head of the Agency for Rural Affairs.

Administrative Services Department is responsible for procurement and competitive tendering. Procurements follow European Legislation and the Act on Market Arrangement of Agricultural Products.

The Agency has invested in e-services and IT systems and the e-services available provide instructions on drafting applications. In further detail, available applications are:

- Vipu-service – e-service for farmers is tailored for the submittal of applications for farmer support, and viewing information on their farms and reference parcels using the map service.
- Support application is used for processing farmers' support and administrating the farm register. Varied updating pressures are directed at the current support application both from the administrative and technological perspectives.
- Hyrrä information system is used for administrating support funded through the Rural Development Programme for Mainland Finland 2014–2020. The submission of applications for financial support for companies and projects in rural areas, agricultural investment subsidies and start-up support for young farmers is also possible through the Hyrrä system. Katso service is utilised for identification of the applicants, which enables applicants to log in to the system using their online banking IDs.
- Other services include Nekkathat supports the School Milk scheme and public administration's e-services.

The Agency also guides, advises and trains partners serving its customers:

- ✓ the Centres for Economic Development Transport and the Environment (ELY Centres)
- ✓ municipalities' co-operation areas and
- ✓ local action groups.

The data security system of the Finnish Agency for Rural Affairs (Mavi) fulfils the requirements of the ISO/IEC 27001:2005 Information Security Management standard.

CONTACT DETAILS

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Email : info@mavi.fi
Website : <http://www.mavi.fi/>

FRANCE

Agence de Services
et de Paiement

makers.

The Service and Payments Agency (ASP) was established as a result of the merger of the AUP (Single Payment Agency) and Cnasea (National Center for the Development of Farm Structures Agriculture). ASP ensures payment of all aid paid to agricultural holdings. The result of this merger is the establishment of an Agency with rich know-how, able to respond quickly and effectively to the demands of the various decision-

ASP is a public administrative institution placed under the double tutelage of the Department of Agriculture, Agri-Food and Forestry and the Ministry of Labor, Employment, Vocational Training and Social Dialogue.

The Agency is administered by a Board of Directors comprising of 12 representatives of the State and 9 representatives of public institutions and professional organizations designated by joint order of the Minister for Agriculture and the Minister for Employment.

It is headed by a Chief Executive Officer appointed by Decree. He is assisted by a Deputy Director-General and a Secretary-General. The Agency is structured in three main divisions under the General Director responsible for administration, agricultural payments and developmental planning. It also operates 17 Regional Directorates with a number of local offices.

Government Procurements undergo consultation and are published online once they have been published in the BOAMP (Bulletin tell16 es 16 d'annonces des tell 16 es publics) and if necessary in the OJEU (Official Journal of the European Union). Procurements may concern negotiated markets, contracts with adapted procedures, open tenders, restricted tenders, competitive dialogues launched by the ASP.

CONTACT DETAILS

- Address** : 2, rue du Maupas - 87040 Limoges Cedex
- Telephone** : 05 55 12 00 00
- Email** : support-mp@asp-public.fr
- Website** : www.asp-public.fr

● GERMANY

The Federal Office of Agriculture and Food (BLE) is a federal authority. Pursuant to the Law on the Implementation of the Common Market Organisation (CMO), the BLE is the German market regulating agency for the common market organisations within the European Union.

The President, as the head of the BLE, manages its operations and represents the BLE externally. The Administrative Council is composed of representatives from the industry, state and federal administrations, and consumer groups. It advises the Federal Office in connection with its specific tasks and it also brings forward proposals. In all issues of principle the Administrative Council is consulted by the BLE, and especially for the nomination of the president and the vice president, or in case of amendments to the statutes. In addition, the Council decides on the establishment of advisory boards whose activities it coordinates. The advisory boards directly advise the BLE's administrative organs in matters relating to each of their specific fields.

The main Departments the Agency is organized in, include the following: Central administrative services, Finance and accounting, Research and innovation, Sustainability, Knowledge management and Agricultural and foreign trade regulations.

The BLE is based in Bonn-Mehlem and operates branches and offices across Germany. BLE branches and relocated units are located in Hamburg, Munich and Weimar. Offices responsible for issues related to quality control are based in Bremerhaven, Frankfurt/Main, Hamburg and Cologne.

As the market regulating agency the BLE is, in particular, concerned with market intervention, private storage, aid measures and market observation. Additionally the Product Contact Point, the BLE provides information about national product legislation in force. The BLE is responsible for tasks relating to the food security and the energy supply in Germany. In many cases the BLE also acts as nationwide accreditation body on behalf of private inspection bodies, for example for the monitoring of organic farms, or for sustainable production of biofuels and bioliquids for generating electricity and heat. In two German federal states, the Rhineland-Palatinate and Saarland, it offers consultations on bioenergy.

No details on standards accreditation were available.

CONTACT DETAILS

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Website : www.ble.de

● GREECE

The Greek Payment Agency (OPEKEPE) has been operating since 2001 and is supervised by the Minister of Agriculture. The Board of OPEKEPE consists of 13 members who are representatives of the Ministry of Finance, Agriculture, Geotechnical Chamber of Greece and OPEKEPE Workers. It is based in Athens and has 6 Regional Directorates that operate either on a subdivision or department level. The key processes of the Agency (payments, checks, financial - administrative - technical support) are coordinated centrally.

The procurement procedures are carried out in accordance with the national legislation for Public Works Contracts, Supplies and Services and the Directives 2014/24/EU and 2014/25/EU of the Department of Administrative and Financial Support.

OPEKEPE, in the frames of its Educational Policy is also active on the field of training both for its personnel and other natural and legal entities working under the Common Agricultural Policy.

OPEKEPE was recently accredited (2016) for the implementation of an Information Security Management System in accordance to the international standard ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : 5 Domokoust, PC. 10445, ATHENS
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Email : www.opekepe.gr
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● HUNGARY

The Agricultural and Rural Development Agency (ARDA) implements the aid instruments financed from both European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), and also national schemes.

The Agency is managed by the President and two vice Presidents. One vice President supervises the Directorates related to IT Services and Support Schemes, while the other one Horizontal and Area-Based Affairs. Departments responsible for International Relations and External Audit Coordination, Financial Management, Legal Affairs and Human Resources are directly under the President. Nineteen County Offices also operate one for each Hungarian county.

**Agricultural and Rural
Development Agency**

Procurements are carried out by the Supply Supervisory Unit under the Department for Budget and Financial Management.

The Agency is accredited for the implementation of an Information Security Management System according to the international standard ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Agricultural and Rural Development Agency, H-1095 Budapest, Soroksáriút 22–24, Postal address: H-1476 Budapest, 100. Pf. 407

Telephone : 00 36 1 219-4593

Email : emva@mvh.gov.hu

Website : www.emva.hu

● IRELAND

In Ireland there is currently one accredited Paying Agency, the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) under the Minister for Agriculture, Food and Marine.

The Management structure of the Department under the Secretary General comprises Assistant Secretaries, the Chief Veterinary Officer, the Chief Agricultural Inspector, the Director of Laboratories and the Director of Information Management and Technology. The Department apart from the Head Office also operates eleven local offices.

Procurements are published under the Freedom of Information Act, Data Protection Act and EU Directives on public procurement.

The following processes are undertaken for public procurement competitions:

Central framework contracts put in place by the Office of Government Procurement or a Public Sector Body procuring on behalf of other public sector bodies. As a background, in accordance with the public sector reform of procurement, the Office of Government Procurement (OGP) is responsible for centralising the public procurement function for the public service. The OGP model envisages the following:

- ✓ that the Public Service will speak with one 'voice' to the market for each category of expenditure or commodity, eliminating duplication of procurement activities across the public services,
- ✓ that the OGP will be the sole vehicle for sourcing common categories and commodities, and
- ✓ where a designated public agency/body retains a sectoral procurement function in accordance with OGP rules, it will establish a single sector procurement function (DAFM has not been assigned a sectoral procurement function).

As a consequence of the foregoing, in circumstances where the OGP or a designated public body has put in place central frameworks for DAFM requirements, the DAFM sources procurement requirements directly from those central contracts.

Quality Management Systems based on the ISO 9001:2008 standard have successfully been implemented in a number of areas of the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine to improve and standardise the procedures and processes used in the delivery of our schemes and services.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Agriculture House, Kildare Street, Dublin 2, DO2 WK12
Telephone : 01 607 2000
Email : info@agriculture.gov.ie
Website : www.agriculture.gov.ie

● ITALY

The AGEA (Agency for Agricultural Payments) was established by Legislative Decree n. 165/99 as a Paying Agency and a Coordination Body. Articles 3, paragraphs 2 and 3 of the same decree regulated the establishment, in regions and autonomous provinces, of bodies that will perform functions of Paying Agencies (eleven paying agencies).

The AGEA as the Italian Coordination Body supports the activities carried out by the paying agencies and ensures the provision of required procedures. The AGEA is also a Paying Agency and has competence for the provision of aid, grants, awards, community interventions etc.

The organisational structure is set in three different organisational units of distinct functions and specifically the offices of the Director and Press and Communication, Administration and Coordination directorates and the Paying Body Office.

By law of 22 December 2001 n. 441 the Paying Body Office was established under the Chief Executive in charge of the paying agency functions, in order to ensure that the Agency's functions of coordination and those of a paying agency should be implemented through separate management and separate accounts. The Paying Body Office ensures the efficiency of the management structure and control of aid, awards and community contributions, except those pertaining to other paying agencies, through the adoption of procedures aimed at a more rational use of resources, tools and means in full compliance with current Community rules.

The Agency also cooperates with other bodies to which specific tasks have been delegated, such as the CAA (the Agricultural Assistance Centers) carrying out support activities in the preparation of applications for admission to the EU and national benefits mandated by the entrepreneurs concerned. The CAA represents the instrument by which the Paying Body ensures constant dialogue with producers and a better and more direct assistance to them for the proper establishment of aid applications.

Procurements are in accordance to EU requirements and the procedure runs according to the amount of the contract.

There was no information on management systems accreditation available.

CONTACT DETAILS

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Telephone : +39 06494991
Email : direttore.coordinationo@agea.gov.it
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● LATVIA

The Rural Support Service is a state administration institution. It was established in 2000, and operates under the supervision of the Ministry of Agriculture in accordance with the Law on Rural Support Service.

Rural Support Service
Republic of Latvia

The Rural Support Service is responsible for the implementation of a unified state and European Union support policy in the sector of agriculture, forestry, fisheries and rural development; it supervises compliance of the sector with laws and regulations and fulfils other functions connected with agriculture and implementation of rural support policy.

It is supervised by the Director and three Deputy Directors responsible for Rural Development, Payments and Administration Management. Internal control, personnel and public relations divisions are directly under the Director, as well as the nine regional offices established in Latvia.

The Rural Support Service offers a series of e-services such as the Electronic Application System (submission of different types of applications for EU and Latvia's state support programs), Seasonal farmers (seasonal farm worker income tax regime) and Diesel fuel for farmer module (application for receiving discounts on diesel fuel used in agricultural work) that are modules in Electronic Application System (EAS).

A procurement division is under the Administrative Department supervised by the Deputy Director.

The procurement procedures are according to Cabinet Regulations No 65 05.02.2008 "Rules of procurement procedures and the application of customer-funded projects" and CM Regulations No. 783 14.07.2009 "Procedure for granting state and European Union support for rural development and fisheries". It supports the applicant (rural entrepreneurs, associations, and other natural legal persons) who wish to receive aid must undertake procurement procedure pursuant to Regulation No. 65, if the investment activities of works estimated contract price is LVL 120,000 or higher (excluding VAT). If the estimated contract price is lower than the limits set out, then a simplified price survey is taken comparing at least two valid tenders and determining the most advantageous one, where the determination criteria is of lower price.

The Rural Support Service of the Republic of Latvia is accredited for the implementation of the Management Systems ISO 9001 and ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Rural Support Service of the Republic of Latvia, Republikaslaukums 2, Rīga, LV-1981, 67095000
Telephone : +37167095000
Email : lad@lad.gov.lv
Website : www.lad.gov.lv

● Lithuania

The National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture (NMA Nacionalinė mokėjimo agentūra prie Žemės ūkio ministerijos) is the only accredited institution managing the measures of support for agriculture, rural development and fisheries. The National Paying Agency was established in 1999 and upon the accession of Lithuania into the European Union in 2004, the Agency became active in the management of the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy measures.

The process of application of a Common Assessment Framework was initiated at the Agency in December 2009.

The organizational structure consists of the Management, 2 Senior Advisers, 10 departments (management, administrative and agricultural support), 4 independent units (administrative and payment controls) and 10 regional support administration units. Public procurements for project implementers is controlled by the Common affairs department – Public procurement unit.

The NPA has successfully accomplished a project related to execution of public procurement: a subsystem has been developed on the NPA website www.nma.lt for the announcement of purchases, executed by the NPA project implementers.

The project started in March 2014 and its objective is to enhance transparency of public procurement processes by creating conditions to publish procurement notices via the NPA website for the NPA project implementers (non-purchasing institutions) who execute purchases. It will not only allow to widen the circle of potential suppliers, but it will also assist the project implementers in the selection of the cheapest possible goods/services/works. The innovative idea and aspirations to introduce transparent processes within the NPA served as a source of motivation for the NPA project team to go ahead with this initiative. The project was successfully accomplished in January 2016.

The Agency is accredited for the implementation of an Information Security Management System according to ISO/IEC 27001:2005 requirements (2009), a Quality Management System in accordance with LST EN ISO 9001:2008 in 2010 and an Environmental Management System LST EN ISO 14001:2005 (2014). The Agency has also been granted the National Quality Prize in the category of big enterprises (Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Lithuania and the Quality Council, 2012).

NPA maintains close business relationships with quite a few EU Member States (Latvia, Estonia, Poland, Czech Republic, France, Romania, Slovenia, Finland, and Netherlands). Cooperation is on-going with the Eastern Partnership countries (Belarus, Moldova) and with the EU candidate countries (Montenegro, Albania, Serbia, Turkey). NPA concluded bilateral cooperation agreements with the paying agencies in Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria and Moldova. The similar agreement with the Ukrainian State Farmers Support Fund is currently under preparation.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Blindžių str. 17, 08111 Vilnius
Telephone : (85) 252 6999
Email : info@nma.lt
Website : www.nma.lt

● LUXEMBURG

The Service d'Economie Rurale (SER) or "Agricultural Economic Service" is a state service established in 1964 and under the responsibility of the Ministry of Agriculture. It is responsible for the application of the Common Agricultural Policy at a national level.

The Law of 21 December 1964 established the SER. The laws of 25 February 1980 and 29 July 1998 on the organization of the SER supplemented the original law of its establishment. In 1975, the SER was given the additional task of managing the compensatory allowance in less-favoured areas within the framework of the application of Council Directive 75/268/ EEC of 28 April 1975 on mountain and hill farming and farming in certain less-favoured areas.

The SER has also been managing the landscape management scheme since 1997, in accordance with Council Regulation (EEC) No 2078/92 of 30 June 1992 on environmentally sound agricultural production methods protecting the natural environment and Regulation (EC) No 1257/1999 on the Promotion of rural development by the European Agricultural Guidance and Guarantee Fund (EAGGF).

The organisational departments of the SER comprise of the Department of Agricultural Accounts and Agricultural Statistics, Department of Economics, Accounting, Business Administration and Inter-company Cooperation and the Department of External Relations and Agricultural Markets.

No information on procurements process or accredited management systems was available.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Service d'Economie Rurale 115, rue de Hollerich, L-1741 Luxembourg, Luxembourg
Telephone :
Email : info@ser.public.lu
Website : www.ser.public.lu

● MALTA

The Malta Agriculture and Rural Payments Agency is established in accordance with Subsidiary Legislation 146.03 Paying Agency Regulations and is set up in accordance with Regulation (EU)No 1306/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulations (EC) Nos 908/2014and907/2014.

It is organised in the following units

- Authorisation Units
- Control Unit
- Quality Control Unit
- Payments Unit
- Accounts Unit
- Support Services
 - Administration
 - IT Solutions
- Accreditation Office
- Internal Audit Service

Public procurement Regulations are according to Subsidiary Legislation 174.04 (1st June, 2010 *LEGAL NOTICE 296 of 2010*). Legislation General Provision rules for governing public contracts are related to their value (less, up to or over €120,000).

On-line applications, farmer registry on-line and details of amounts received by Maltese beneficiaries under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) are the available e-applications by the ARPA.

The Agency operates a Quality Control Unit and implements a Management System, but there is no information available on its accreditation.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address	: Ministry for Sustainable Development, the Environment and Climate Change, Agriculture and Rural Payments Agency
Telephone	: 22926148
Email	: https://secure2.gov.mt/MRRA-PA/contactus?l=1
Website	: https://secure2.gov.mt/MRRA-PA/home

● NETHERLANDS

Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend
Nederland

Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO.nl) encourages entrepreneurs in sustainable, agrarian, innovative and international business. It helps with grants, finding business partners, know-how and compliance with laws and regulations.

The aim is to improve opportunities for entrepreneurs and strengthen their position.

Netherlands Enterprise Agency is part of the Ministry of Economic Affairs and works at the instigation of ministries and the European Union. Some activities of the Commodities Boards are also included. The Agency works in the Netherlands and abroad with governments, knowledge centres, international organisations and countless other partners.

Apart from the Head office in Assen, five more offices operate around the country in Hague, Deventer, Roermond, Utrecht & Zwolle.

The procurement process of the National Entrepreneurial Netherlands (RVO.nl) follows national rules of Public procurement (Tender Ned-<https://www.tenderned.nl/>). For individual contracts under € 50,000 excluding VAT, usually only one quotation is requested to a vendor. For purchases above that amount as a rule a tender is requested to at least three suppliers. For large orders (above the European threshold) RVO.nl must launch a public tender and publish.

Digital services available include eLoket the digital counter to apply for grants and Mijn.rvo.nl the digital counter for farmers.

No information on the accreditation of Management Systems or the organisational structure of the Agency where available.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : RVO.nl , P.O. Box 322, 9400 AH Assen, The Netherlands
Telephone : +31 70 379 80
Email : <https://www.rvo.nl/contactformulier-rijksdienst-voor-ondernemend-nederland-rvonl-wssl?herkomst=http%3A//www.rvo.nl/over-ons/over-ons/wat-doet-rvonl/contact>
Website : www.rvo.nl

● POLAND

The Agency for Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture (ARMA) was established in 1994 with the aim to support agriculture and rural development in Poland.

Agencja Restrukturyzacji
i Modernizacji Rolnictwa

Following Poland's decision to join the European Union, ARMA has been designated by the Government of the Republic of Poland to perform the role of an accredited paying agency.

The Agency is headed by a President appointed by the Prime Minister of the Republic of Poland upon a joint request by the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development and the Minister of Finance. The structure of ARMA comprises three levels: the Headquarters, 16 Regional Offices in each region (voivodship) and 314 Local Offices.

The Agency, as the performer of agricultural policy, cooperates with its supervising body - the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. At the same time, as an administrator of public funds, ARMA falls under the supervision of the Ministry of Finance.

The scope of ARMA's operation involves both the implementation of instruments co-financed from the European Union's budget as well as providing of aid from national funds.

The main beneficiaries of measures implemented by ARMA are farmers, inhabitants of rural areas, entrepreneurs from the agri-food sector and local governments. The Agency also provides aid to entities operating in the fisheries sector.

The Agency is accredited for the implementation of an Information Security Management System ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : ul. Poleczki 33, 02-822 Warszawa
Telephone : 800 38 00 84
Email : info@arimr.gov.pl
Website : www.arimr.gov.pl

● PORTUGAL

The Institute for the Financing of Agriculture and Fisheries - IFAP IP was created by Decree-Law no. 87/2007, and was established after the merger of the Institute for Financing and Support for the Development of Agriculture and Fisheries (IFADAP) and the National Institute for Agricultural Intervention and Guarantee (INGA). Subsequently, through Decree-Law no. 195/2012, of August 23 (document rectified by Declaration of Rectification No. 50/2012), this body was restructured. Portaria nº 393/2012, of November 29, determines the internal organization of IFAP services and approves its statutes.

IFAP, I.P., is a public institute of special regime, under the terms of the law, integrated in the indirect administration of the State, endowed with administrative and financial autonomy and its own assets.

IFAP, I.P., continues the attributions of the Ministry of Agriculture and the Sea (MAM), under the oversight and tutelage of the respective minister. The supervision and oversight of IFAP, IP, regarding their financial management, are carried out jointly by the members of the Government responsible for the areas of agriculture and fisheries and finance, according to Decree-Law no. 18/2014, of February 4.

The organization is supervised by the a Board of Directors assisted by a Security Council for Information Systems, a Strategic planning board and an Audit board. Support, control, management, financial, legal and administration duties are allocated to nine Departments.

Public procurements and contracts procedures are set by the Public Contracts Code (CPC), approved by Decree-Law no. 18/2008 of 29 January. All procedures foreseen in the CPC are carried out via an electronic platform, BizGov and all interested parties will necessarily have to go through an accession / certification process. Access to this platform is free and tenders must be submitted with reference to the procedure of the respective public tender, with publication in the newspaper Diário da República or in the Official Journal of the European Union.

The Agency is accredited for the implementation of an Information Security Management System ISO 27001.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Rua Castilho, nº. 45-51, 1269-164 LISBOA
Telephone : 213 846 000
Email : ifap@ifap.pt
Website : www.ifap.min-agricultura.pt

● ROMANIA

Ministerul Agriculturii și Dezvoltării Rurale

Paying Agency for Rural Investment (AFIR) operates according to Government Emergency Ordinance no. 41 of 18 June 2014 on the establishment, organization and functioning of the Agency for Rural Investment Finanțarea by reorganizing the Agency of Payments for Rural Development and Fishing (APDRP), approved by Law 43 of March 17,

2015.

The Agency is managed by the CEO and the coordinating Directorates are of Programme Coordination, Internal Audit, Control and Fraud prevention, Legal Department and Human Resources. Three Deputy Directors manage the Departments relative to payments, management and administration.

The Paying Agency for Rural Investment (AFIR) consists of 13 specialized central directions, 8 Regional Centres and 41 District Offices.

The Department of Assets is responsible for contracting and procurement procedures and the procedures for authorizing payments. The process of public procurements is carried out in force of Law No.98 / 2016 on public procurement; Law no. 100/2016 on concessions for works and services concessions, Law no.101 / 2016 on remedies and appeals concerning the award of public procurement contracts, sector contracts, works concession contracts and service concession, and for the organization and functioning of the National Council for Solving Complaints; and Decision no. 395 of June 2, 2016 approving the Methodological Norms for the application of provisions concerning the award of public procurement contract / framework agreement of Law. 98/2016 on public procurement.

The Agency achieved in March 2013, the accreditation of the quality standard ISO 20000-1: 2011, applicable to IT Service Management System. Additionally on June 2014 AFIR was accredited on the implementation of an Information Security Management System according to the international standard ISO 27001:2013.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Paying Agency for Rural Investment, Headquarters – Bucharest, Str. StirbeiVoda, nr. 43, sector 1, București

Telephone : +40 213 101 635

Email : promovare@apdrp.ro

Website : www.apdrp.ro

SLOVAKIA

Pursuant to Act No 473/2003 Coll. on the Agricultural Paying Agency, on farming subsidization and on amending and supplementing certain laws, the APA was established by 1 December 2003. The Agricultural Intervention Agency together with SAPARD Agency and Ministry of Agriculture of the Slovak Republic Section of Agricultural Paying Agency were merged into APA. Activities associated with the pre-accession programme SAPARD had been provided by APA.

APA is a budgetary organization involved in financial relations with the budget of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic.

As the accredited body of the state administration provides administration of support in agriculture, food industry, forestry and fisheries from the state budget, as well as for agriculture, rural development and fisheries according to the special conditions.

The main tasks of APA include collecting applications for funding from RDP and direct subsidies for approved assistance schemes, evaluation of eligibility for funding, payment of funding, audit into compliance with conditions for use of requested funding and monitoring of compliance with contract conditions.

The paying agency has been authorised to establish the offices with stated scope of activities and operational area falling under it to provide execution of the activities.

The Director General manages the Agency and supervises the Internal Control, Financial, Management and Human Resources Division and relative departments. He is assisted by an Executive Director responsible for Budget and Facility Management Department. A Deputy Director for Regional Offices supervises and coordinates the 17 regional offices APA operates.

Agricultural Paying Agency in Bratislava (the "PPA") is a contracting authority pursuant to § 6.1 point. a) of Act no. 25/2006 Z.z. Public Procurement amending and supplementing certain acts, as amended (the "Public Procurement Act"). Award of contracts for goods, execution of works and services under the Law on public procurement are carried out in accordance with applicable Organizational Order Department Procurement Section of economic governance, property and budget of the Agricultural Payment Agency. PPA contracting authority publishes information on public procurement pursuant to § 49 of the Law on Public Procurement in the profile of the contracting authority, which is available on the website of the Office for Public Procurement.

Agricultural Paying Agency is accredited for the implementation of an information security management system according to ISO 27001:2013.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : APA - Agricultural Paying Agency, Dobrovičova 12, 815 26 Bratislava, Slovak Republic

Telephone : +421 918 612 552

Email : info@apa.sk

Website : www.apa.sk

● SLOVENIA

REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
 MINISTRSTVO ZA KMETIJSTVO,
 GOZDARSTVO IN PREHRANO
 AGENCIJA REPUBLIKE SLOVENIJE ZA
 KMETIJSKE TRGE IN RAZVOJ PODEŽELJA

The Agency of the Republic of Slovenia for Agricultural Markets and Rural Development has been operating since 2000 as a body within the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food of the Republic of Slovenia. It was established for the implementation of programs related to the agricultural policy reform, for alignment to the EU common agricultural policy and execution of SAPARD pre-accession assistance payments.

The Agency holds the role of the only accredited paying agency in Slovenia for the allocation of Common Agricultural Policy funds in the field of agriculture, food-processing industry and rural development.

The agency is managed and supervised by the Director General. He is assisted by a Deputy Director General and the main Departments are General Affairs Service, Service for Information Management and Technology, Agricultural Markets Section, Direct Payments Section, Rural Development Section, Financial Service, Internal Audit and Control Service.

The Legal affairs and Public Procurement Department implements measures on the basis of national and EU legal acts (acts, decrees, regulations, rules and guidance). Additionally it is responsible for the public procurement process including the preparation of various contracts concluded for different purposes i.e. supply of goods and services.

In the field of information systems the Agency is accredited on Information technology — Security techniques — Code of practice for information security controls according to the International Standard ISO/IEC 27002:2013.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Agency of the Republic of Slovenia for Agricultural Markets and Rural Development
 Dunajska 160 , SI-1000 Ljubljana or p.p. 189 SI-1001 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Telephone : +386 (0)1 580 77 92

Email : aktrp@gov.si

Website : www.arsktrp.gov.si

SPAIN

The Co-ordinating Paying Agency in Spain is the Spanish Agrarian Guarantee Fund (Fondo Español de Garantía Agraria - FEGA) that is an Autonomous Organisation under the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment and the General Secretariat of Agriculture and Food.

The Agency is supervised / administered by a President with the rank of Director General, whose appointment is made by a Royal Decree, agreed in Council of Ministers, at the proposal of the Minister of Agriculture, Food and Environment. The Departments of the Agency include management support, consultancy and financial control.

Procurements are handled by the General Secretary and are announced in the State's procurement platform the FEGA web site according to EU Regulations and national legislation.

Management of EAGGF payments in Spain is carried out in accordance with the distribution of competencies among public administrations (Central Public Administration and Autonomous Regions). This distribution of powers has given rise to a system, the Spanish European Funds Management System, comprising of FEGA and the Autonomous Region Paying Agencies.

In this system, FEGA undertakes coordination functions in order to encourage harmonised application of community dispositions and centralize the information that must be made available to the Commission of the European Union, as well as those representing Spain before European agencies responsible for financing the CAP. The Paying Agencies of the Autonomous Regions (17) perform the functions of management and payment of the subsidies under their responsibility, contributing their experience to better adapt the general regulations of applying subsidies to the peculiarities of each of the territories in which they act.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Unidades Administrativas c/ Beneficencia, 8. MADRID-28004
Telephone : 91 347 65 00
Email : www.fega.es/contacta
Website : www.fega.es

● SWEDEN

The Swedish Board of Agriculture – Paying Agency Function is the Government's expert authority in the agro-food sector and is responsible for all matters related to agriculture and horticulture. This means monitoring and analysing the agricultural sector and keeping the Government informed, as well as implementing political decisions within its field of activity.

The Swedish Board of Agriculture consists of management, Director General's office and four Divisions Staff, Service and Control, Paying Agency Function and District Veterinarians. Paying Agency Function operates in Departments for Support Matters, Management and Department under the Divisional Director.

Regarding public procurements, they are carried out by the Division of Market Support of the Swedish Board of Agriculture. Relative legislation is in accordance with the Commission Regulations (EC) No 1017/2010 and No. 1272/2009 and the Swedish Regulations (SJVFS 2010:70)

No details on Management Systems accreditation were available.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Jordbruksverket, 551 82 Jönköping, Sweden
Telephone : : +46 771 223 223
Email : Kundtjänst@jordbruksverket.se
Website : www.jordbruksverket.se/swedishboardofagriculture

● UNITED KINGDOM

The Co-ordinating Body for the implementation of EU regulations across the UK is the UKCB. UKCB was set up by the Secretary of State for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs; the Scottish ministers; the Welsh ministers and the Department of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Northern Ireland Executive, acting collectively, to carry out the functions of the Co-ordinating Body, as defined in Article 7.4 of Regulation 1306/2013. It is an independent executive unit that supports regional paying agencies to administer CAP in the UK.

UKCB is the sole point of contact with the European Commission on certain specified aspects of the EU's agricultural funds and manages the online publication of amounts paid to CAP beneficiaries by UK paying agencies. In addition it is the UK Certifying Authority for the UK European Maritime Fisheries Fund (EMFF) 2014 to 2020, holding responsibility for the accurate certification of funds expended in the UK.

There are four regional accredited Paying Agencies in the UK: the Rural Payments Agency (RPA), the Scottish Government Rural Payments & Inspections Directorate (SGRPID), the Welsh Government (WG) and the Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA) in Northern Ireland. A Paying Agency may delegate certain functions to other bodies, but remains responsible for accounting for all its payments under CAP schemes.

UKCB reports to a Management Board, consisting of 4 individuals nominated by Ministers and the Director. The chairmanship of the board rotates between the 4 ministers' representatives. The Departments of the Agency include management support and financial control. Corporate support services (including procurements) are provisioned by RPA and legal services by Defra legal advisers.

Procurements at RPA are managed through the Government Procurement Service (GPS) on www.gov.uk/call-charges. The process is according to EU legislation and the Agency has also implemented a sustainable procurement policy following specific guidelines established by DEFRA.

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Co-ordinating body, North Gate House, 21-23 Valpy Street Reading, RG1 1AF
Telephone : 020 776 42161
Email : enquiries@ukcb.gsi.gov.uk
Website : www.gov.uk/government/organisations/uk-co-ordinating-body

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Rural Payments Agency, PO Box 69, Reading, RG1 3YD
Telephone : 03000 200 301
Email : ruralpayments@defra.gsi.gov.uk
Website : www.gov.uk/government/organisations/rural-payments-agency

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Scottish Government Rural Payments & Inspections Directorate (SGRPID), Saughton House, RPID Communications, C1 Spur, Broomhouse Drive, Edinburgh

Telephone :

Email : RPID_Payment_Enquiries@gov.scot

Website : www.ruralpayments.org/publicsite/futures

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : Welsh Government (WG), Cathays Park, Cardiff, CF10 3NQ

Telephone : +44 1443 845500

Email : CustomerHelp@Wales.GSI.Gov.UK

Website : <http://gov.wales/>

CONTACT DETAILS

Address : **Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA)**, Dundonald House, Upper Newtownards Road, Ballymiscaw, Belfast BT4 3SB

Telephone : +44(0) 28 9049 5780

Email : daera.helpline@daera-ni.gov.uk

Website : www.daera-ni.gov.uk

1.2 Agricultural consultants

This chapter deals with the agricultural consulting services provided to the EU farmers and agricultural firms. These services are mostly offered by private consulting firms, freelance agronomists and public authorities, as well as farm-based organizations.

The agricultural consulting services refer to advices on promoting and trading products, compliance to national and European legislation, implementation of CAP requirements, monitoring of farms, environmental adaptation, new technologies, training and education etc.

In the **UK**, agricultural consultants generally provide services of three categories: (a) Compliance and application services for government schemes, particularly the Basic Payments Scheme and current environmental schemes. This can range from informal advice and query resolution, to completing the whole process on behalf of the farmer. (b) Strategic advice: this service is more on the lines of a management consultant, and seeks to enable understanding of the effect practical/operational decisions made by the farmer, on the financial performance of farm business. Relevant decisions would include machinery policy, cropping programme, expansion over a greater area of land and many others. (c) Management advice: this service provides more detailed advice on aspects of the ongoing farm business. It includes advice on grain selling, employment, and crop growing. It also includes management of joint operations between farmers, such as contract farming agreements and short term tenancy arrangements. Clients tend to be larger farmers, perhaps above 200Ha. In the east of the UK most full time farmers would cover at least this area. In the west and north, where farm size is smaller and more concentrated on milk and meat production, income is often quite low and money spent on consultants is not a high priority. An exception to this, is dairy farming, where technical consultants are widely used.

In **Greece**, agricultural consultants are either freelancers or employees at consulting firms. The provided services are associated with programme funding, farm monitoring, product trade/promoting and technical farm - related issues. Furthermore, a few years ago private entities were certified by the Greek Paying Agency (OPEKEPE)¹ for the Basic Payments Scheme (BPS). Services are mostly provided to individual farmers and agricultural cooperatives. In the case of big farming companies, they have specific departments providing consultancy services. There is no national association of agricultural consultants, in the country. However, the Hellenic Association of Management Consulting Firms (SESMA)² was founded in 1991. Additionally, there is a national association of entities certified for the BPS. The Agronomist Chamber of Greece constitutes an official association of agronomists although its members are not only agricultural consultants but also agronomists who work in the private and public sector, offering a variety of services.

In **Lithuania**, there are three types of agricultural advisors: (a) the independent advisors, (b) the freelancer advisors and (c) the sales advisors. In the first case, independent advisors are mostly employees of the Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service (LAAS), providing services to a great number of Lithuanian farmers and it is the only independent consultancy service. LAAS is also responsible for the implementation of agricultural policy. Freelance advisors provide services for a short term. In particular, the agreements between farmers and consultants enter into force only for the following cultivated period. The last category, sales advisors, constitute employees of commercial enterprises aiming to promote their products. The second and the third type of advisors do not provide services on identification of agricultural parcels, farm monitoring and precision farming. There are also lots of private consulting companies with a mixed orientation, providing agricultural consulting (though not exclusively).

¹<http://www.opekepe.gr/>

²<http://www.sesma.gr/en/>

In **Serbia**, agricultural consultants are agronomists working at Municipal advisory centers of agriculture and rural development. Their main objective is to build bridges between farmers and the Ministry of Agriculture and Environmental Protection, providing advisory services 24/7 to farmers and answering their questions on latest regulations brought by the Ministry, as well as other farm – related issues, including agricultural subsidies. Freelancer consultants are rare. Occasionally, the Ministry of Agriculture and Environmental Protection collaborates with individual consultants in order to offer services in specific Ministry projects. Furthermore, individual consultants work at large farm holdings as regular employees. There is no national or regional association of agricultural consultants or agronomists, although, the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops organizes regularly conferences and workshops, aiming at gathering agricultural consultants. In the Province of Vojvodina, there are 13 advisory centers which operate under the Agricultural Advisory Service of Vojvodina and respectively there are 33 advisory centers in Central Serbia. In addition, there are four certification bodies in organic farming.

In **Spain**, agricultural consultants are agronomists who provide services on funding, accountancy, direct payments and technical farm-related issues. Agricultural consultants refer as public entities owned by the Regional Governments or as departments of big agricultural cooperatives. They are also technical supporters of farmers' trade unions or big private enterprises. In regional level operates a considerable number of public entities providing consultancy services. In Navarra, the Institute for Agri - food Technology and Infrastructure (INTIA) is a public company attached to the Department of Rural Development, Environment and Local Administration of the Government of Navarra. Furthermore, according to the European Federation of Agricultural Consultants (EFAC)³ a coordination entity owned by five advisory Centers and an agri-food foundation⁴ with the objective of coordinating the activities of the enterprises and maintaining the relationships with other public or private initiatives, was founded in the Basque country. In the Autonomous Communities of Spain⁵, there are some public entities providing in some cases, consultancy services. In Spain, there is no national association of agricultural consultants. Farmers' trade unions and their consulting departments are composed in National Federations.

In **Belgium**, there is a variety of consultants and consulting companies which provide agriculture and farm management services. These refer to advices on funding, the CAP, rural development, investments, accountancy, taxes, farm development investments, as well as technical support in production. The services are provided to individual farmers (either small or large scaled farms), farmers' cooperatives and associations and big farming companies (producers, processors, distributors etc.). Other type of services relate to technical assistance and capacity building of public or semi - public institutions working within the agricultural sector.

In **Bulgaria**, at the end of 1999 was established the National Agricultural Advisory Services (NAAS). The main approach of NAAS was to prepare for the new duties regarding the CAP. Furthermore, NAAS provide farmers with information and consultancy services concerning with EU standards in fields of plant growing, environmental protection, funding programs etc. (Dirimanova V., 2014). In addition, during the last years private advisory firms have emerged rapidly due to the ongoing needs of farmers especially for supporting through rural development measures. The provide services by these firms are mostly used by large scale farms⁶.

³<http://www.efac.net/>

⁴ <http://www.hazi.es/eu/>

⁵ Ifapa (Andalucía), Neiker (Pais Vasco), Cida (Rioja), Irta (Cataluña), Imidra (Madrid), Iriaf (Castilla la Mancha), Itacyl (Castilla León), Imida (Murcia), IVIA (Valencia)

⁶ Dirimanova, V. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Bulgaria. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

In the **Czech Republic**, the Farm Advisory Service (FAS) system provides services from general to professional advisory level and all kind of services in between. Information is provided through inter-connected websites. The advisory system has four levels constituting an integrated system. Advisory services are offered by various bodies. These bodies referred to accredited advisors, NGOs, institutes or professional consultants. In addition, consulting services are also provided by private consulting firms where their clients are mostly large farmers⁷.

In **Denmark**, operates the Danish Agricultural Advisory Service (DAAS). It constitutes a partnership made up of 60 local advisory centers and a national center. The partnership employs approximately 3,400 professionals. Today, DAAS is one of the leading agricultural advisory services in Europe⁸. Furthermore, there are two large private advisory companies which are owed by farmers and the Knowledge Centre for Agriculture and the Dutch DLV Plant respectively. In addition, there are independent companies specializing in advisory services in production and business management⁹.

In **Germany**, there are consulting enterprises which are related with various sections of economy. In the agricultural sector, provision of services is offered by enterprises which exclusively offering advices of this sector or by specific departments of enterprises with mixed oriented services. The Main Association of Agricultural Tax Consultants and Agricultural Surveyors (HLBS), also operates, providing information in subjects such as taxation, auditing and agricultural evaluation. The HLBS is recognized by the Federal Ministry for Nutrition, Agriculture and Consumer Affairs as the only professional organization within the country whose members carry out accounting and auditing services for agricultural businesses, as well as advising businesses on all aspects of agriculture and business management¹⁰.

In **Estonia**, the advisory services are provided by the 15 local advisory centers, which are independent organizations, but mostly by NGOs. These centers are coordinated by the Rural Development Foundation. In 2013, there were 109 certified advisers in agriculture, 67 advisers in forestry and 8 in community development. In Estonia, consulting services are also provided by foreigners. Their presence increases the competitiveness due to the considerable proportion of consulting market they hold¹¹.

In **Ireland**, the provided agricultural consultancy services referred to farm technical advices in all farming subjects, from management and set-up services, to environmental consultancy and laboratory analysis of agricultural products and inputs¹². There is a vast number of private enterprises, small or large, in the agricultural consulting sector. The research also revealed the Agricultural Consultants Association (ACA)¹³ which has 144 professional members and 271 professional, technical and administration staff employed. In 2010 it was estimated that its members provided consultancy services to 44,500 farmers, making ACA the largest advisory body. In addition, the “Teagasc” – the Agriculture and Food Development Authority – is the national body which provides research, advisory and training services to the agriculture and food industry

⁷ Pulkrábek J., Pazderu K. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Czech Republic. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

⁸http://www.efac.net/?page_id=12

⁹ Madsen-Østerbye J. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Denmark. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

¹⁰http://www.efac.net/?page_id=18

¹¹ Korpa V., Tisenkopfs T. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Estonia. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

¹² Prager, K.; Thomson, K. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in the Republic of Ireland. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

¹³<http://aca.ie/>

and rural communities¹⁴. The Teagasc Advisory Service, through a nationwide office network, organized into 12 regional units, is providing local services to all its customers.

In **France**, the consulting services are referred to agricultural firms' management, technical advices, trainings and educational subjects on farming and new agricultural business - plans for collective entities e.g. common use of technical equipment, common investments etc. In the private sector there are only a few consulting firms. Some of them are individual consultants or SMEs. The individual consultants mostly collaborate with farmers' and producers' associations, cooperatives and agricultural enterprises¹⁵. Furthermore, in 2006 20 private firms set-up an association named "Pole for Independent Agricultural Advice-PCIA"¹⁶.

In **Italy**, mostly medium and large farms collaborate with private advisors, either in an on-going basis, or periodically. Only in the wine sector even the smallest businesses have an enologist consultant. The last few years, due to the increased demand by producers to apply for national and European funding programmes, the Italian consultancy sector was expanded. The private advisors work individually or in companies. The Foundation for agricultural advisory services (Fondagri)¹⁷ was founded in 2007. It is a network of freelance advisors, working across all Italian regions, with main objective to participate in the Farm Advisory System measures of RDPs¹⁸.

In **Cyprus**, consultancy services are provided by private firms or freelancer agronomists. Some of them were accredited in order to drawn up business plans for funding schemes in the framework of the 2014-2020 Rural Development Program.

In **Latvia**, consultancy services are provided by both the public and the private sector, as well as, farmers' and societal organizations. The largest agricultural and rural advisory organization is the Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre (LRATC)¹⁹ which consists of 26 entrepreneurship consultants at regional offices and 125 rural development advisers based in local municipalities. In the private sector, there are only a few consulting firms, providing advices to producers²⁰.

In **Luxembourg**, the agricultural advisory sector is consisted of public institutions, agricultural chambers, several farmer-based organizations and private consulting companies. The national consulting market grew in the last 10-20 years. During that period plenty of consulting firms were set up²¹.

In **Hungary**, due to the presence of public authorities which offer free of charge services, private firms are not widespread in the agricultural consulting sector. Large scaled farms mostly attach agreements with private firms. The most well-known advisory programme is "the village extension service", which outset in the 1990s. 600 advisors who are employed as public servants allocated to serve 1-20 villages, each one offering free of charge advices to farmers. Their services include not only advices, but also state control over the farmers according to EU regulations²².

¹⁴<https://www.teagasc.ie/>

¹⁵ Labarthe, P. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in France. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

¹⁶<http://www.pcia.fr/>

¹⁷ <http://www.fondazioneconsulenza.it/>

¹⁸ Caggiano, M. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Italy. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

¹⁹<http://new.llkc.lv/>

²⁰ Šūmane S., Grīviņš M., Tisenkopfs T. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Latvia. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

²¹ Paul, C., Ndah, H.T. Knierim, A., (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Luxembourg. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

²² Kozári, J. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Hungary. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

The Farm Advisory Services Co-operative Ltd²³, operates in **Malta**, providing services referred to statutory management requirements, agricultural and environmental EU Regulation, occupational safety standards, applicable good farming practices, code of good agricultural practices, compliance with Directives in the framework of cross compliance, CAP payments and rural development measures²⁴.

In the **Netherlands**, the Vereniging Agrarische Bedrijfsadviseurs (VAB)²⁵ is the recognized professional association for agricultural business advisors. VAB members are unique users of the Farm Advisory System RVO, which gives access to European agricultural subsidies (CAP funding projects). In addition, the VAB provides certification for agricultural business advisors. The DLV Advisory Group is the largest consulting firm in the Netherlands. It employs almost 500 people who offer ongoing consultancy to farmers assisting them in technical and managerial issues²⁶.

In **Austria**, the consulting services to farmers are provided by advisory organizations or through the agricultural chambers, operating in all provinces. Due to the fact that chambers are the most important representative schemes for producers, they constitute the basic resource for consulting services to farmers. "Bio-Austria", the main association of organic farmers, provides also a wide range of advisory tasks²⁷. Furthermore, there are some independent organizations in agricultural consulting which held a small proportion of the consulting market²⁸.

In **Poland**, agricultural consulting services are offered by the Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinow (with three regional divisions), the 16 provincial advisory centers, agricultural chambers, as well as, by private advisory organizations and numerous NGOs²⁹.

In **Portugal**, there is considerable number of private consultancy firms providing advices to producers. The services offered, relate to technical advices, preparation of agricultural investments projects, subsidies, training, information exchange, project planning new technologies etc. There are also a lot of micro and small consulting firms offering services in specific areas such as vineyards and wine, forestry, irrigation, environment, agro tourism etc.³⁰. Additionally, there are advisors working as regular employees in farm-based organizations.

The **Romanian** agricultural consultancy refers to assistance in accessing funding and technical assistance in developing agricultural works and promoting various agricultural practices. It is also defined by two main components: the public and private sector³¹. The National Agency for Agricultural Consultancy was founded in 1998 as a governmental compartment of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Rural Development. In 2009, the Agency was reorganized in order to form the Agricultural County Chambers³² with the purpose of offering free agricultural consulting for investors and local farmers on a national level³³. The private

²³<http://maltacooperativefederation.coop/about-us/maltese-cooperatives-members-of-mcf/farm-advisory-services-coop-ltd/>

²⁴ Cristiano S., Proietti P. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Malta. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

²⁵<http://www.vabnet.nl/>

²⁶ Caggiano, M. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in The Netherlands. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

²⁷<https://www.bio-austria.at/>

²⁸ Opancar, Christopher (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Austria. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

²⁹ Kania J., Vinohradnik K., Tworzyk A. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Poland. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

³⁰ Baptista, A.; Cristovão, A.; Koehnen, T.; Madureira, L.; Pires, M. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in Portugal. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

³¹<http://www.madr.ro/docs/agricultura/consultata/raport-sintetic-privind-activitatile-de-consultanta2015.pdf>

³²<http://www.madr.ro/docs/ind-alimentara/prezentare-activitate-consultanta-agricola.pdf>

³³ Romania has 41 counties, each with its own county seat (similar to a "capital") and various numbers of cities, communes and villages (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Counties_of_Romania)

consultancies offer services mainly in the area of accessing funding, particularly in elaborating applications, financial planning, project implementation and regulations complying. The 416 entities listed in the AFIR³⁴ database offer consultancy for various areas of activity and it is difficult to estimate what percentage is specialized exclusively in agricultural consulting. At the present moment, it seems, that the private market in agricultural consulting in Romania equals funding accessing for expansion of existing businesses and establishment of new ones. There are also several larger enterprises specialized in offering technical consultancy services for agricultural businesses.

In **Slovenia**, the most well recognized organization in agricultural consulting operates within the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry. It consists of 8 territorial Agricultural and Forestry Institutes and 59 local units and employs over 300 advisors in different interest fields. There are also private professional advisors which keep a small proportion of the consulting³⁵.

In **Finland**, "ProAgria"³⁶ is the leading advisory organization, covering the whole country and the organization gets almost the 80% of the Ministry's subsidy for offering agricultural advising service. Besides ProAgria there are 7 agricultural advising organizations in which are independent, but with a cooperation agreement with the ProAgria Group. These are the Finnish Poultry Association, the Work Efficiency Institute (TTS), the Central Organisation for Finnish Horticulture, the Association for Finnish Beef Farmers, the Association of Organic Farming, the Association for Trotting and Horse Breeding (Hippos) and the Finnish Fur Breeders' Association. Furthermore, private agricultural entrepreneurs also operate. In addition, the Association of Private Rural Advisors has been created, consisting of private advisors who working independently³⁷.

In **Sweden**, the agricultural consultancy sector can be divided in three main categories: (a) the commercial advisory services, (b) the selling advisory which is offered as part of selling inputs to producers and (c) free advisory services which are paid by the public. Today there are 60-70 private or farmer owned advisory providers in the market. Many of these are local actors with less than 10 employees³⁸.

³⁴<http://www.afir.info/>

³⁵ Erhart, V. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in the Republic of Slovenia. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

³⁶<https://www.proagria.fi/>

³⁷ Lehto D. (2014): AKIS and advisory services in the Republic of Finland. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

³⁸ Yngwe K. (2014): Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems in Sweden. Report for the AKIS inventory (WP3) of the PRO AKIS project. Online resource: www.proakis.eu/publicationsandevents/pubs

1.3 Farmers

In the section below, a brief analysis regarding agricultural sector data relative to the crop output level of European Union countries is presented. The data correspond to three cultivation periods from 2013 to 2015. The analysis gives an overview of indicators on crop output, average size per holdings, crop production area, AWUs³⁹ (referred as labor force), amount of direct payments and number of beneficiaries.

Spain, Lithuania and Greece are mainly crop output countries. In particular, in **Greece** the 73.3% of national agricultural output corresponds to crop output. The country has one of the lowest average size per holding in the EU (6.8 ha) while the crop production area reaches 4.8 million ha. Furthermore, Greece owns the seventh position between EU countries having an agricultural labor force of 442,000 people. The total amount of direct payments is almost 2.2 billion EUR which are received by 709,270 beneficiaries.

Spain is also a mainly crop output country with a relevant percentage of 62.5%. It has the second largest crop production area between EU countries reaching 23.9 million ha and the average size per holding is 24.1 ha. The labor force is 819,000 people. Spain receives also one of the largest amounts of direct payments at about 5.1 billion EUR with 870 thousand beneficiaries of aids.

In **Lithuania**, the crop output holds 64.7% of the total agricultural output. The crop production cultivated area is 3 million ha and the average size per holding is 16.7 ha. In farming 151,000 people work and the beneficiaries of aids are 148.5 thousand. The total amount of direct payments is 375.8 million EUR.

United Kingdom has one of the lowest rates of crop output (39.9%). However the country is ranked to one of the highest positions among EU countries in total crop production area which is almost 17.1 million ha. It also has the second largest average size per holding in the EU (93.6 ha). The labor force is 293 thousand people. The UK receives also a notable amount of direct payments of almost 3.2 billion EUR. The aids are distributed to 175,700 beneficiaries.

³⁹ Annual Working Units (AWUs) correspond to the work performed by one person who is occupied on an agricultural holding on a full-time basis (EUROSTAT - GLOSSARY).

In the countries of Southern Europe, the rates of crop output are varied. The highest rates are held by France, Italy and Portugal. In addition, **France** is the country with the highest crop production area in the EU with 29.1 million ha and the highest amount of direct payments at about 7.7 billion EUR which are received by 358,230 beneficiaries. The French crop output represents 62.8% of the total agricultural output. The average size per holding is 58.7 ha and the labor force is 768,000 people.

Italy has also one of the highest rates of crop output in the EU which corresponds to 65.6% of the total national agricultural output and a considerable amount of total crop area of 12.6 million ha. The average size per holding is 12 ha. The labor force is 1,120,000 people placing Italy in the third position among EU countries and the second regarding the number of beneficiaries which is approximately 1.2 million. Direct payments amount 3.2 billion EUR.

In **Portugal**, the crop output is 58.2% of the total agricultural output. The crops area accounts 3.7 million ha and the average size per holding is 13.8 ha. The labor force is 256,000 people. The amount of direct payments reaches almost 634.9 million EUR being distributed to 173,310 beneficiaries.

The crop output in **Cyprus** accounts for 51.1% of the total agricultural output. The crop area is 126,470 ha and the average size per holding only 3.1 ha which is the second lowest between the EU countries. The labor force reaches 24,000 people. The beneficiaries of direct payments are 33 thousand people, while the amount of direct payments is 51.7 million EUR.

In **Malta**, the 44.1% of the total agricultural output is crop output. Malta also constitutes the smallest country regarding crop production land indicators. In particular, the total crop land is 11,690 ha, with an average size of holdings only 1.2 ha. The labor force is 5,000 people, the second lowest in the EU. The lowest amount of direct payments is given to Malta and corresponds to 5.3 million EUR; the beneficiaries of aids are 6,070 people.

In Central Europe, the countries show also a variance in crop output proportions. Specifically, Germany, Netherlands, Belgium and Poland hold percentages approximately between 50 – 55%. On the other hand, Luxemburg and Austria hold 45.6% and 47.3% respectively, while Hungary and Czech Republic have 64.4% and 61.4%.

In **Germany**, the area of crops is 16.7 million ha, while the average size per holding reaches 58.6 ha. The farming labor force is 496,000 people. The amount of direct payments is almost 5.1 billion EUR, the third highest in the EU, which is distributed to 320,290 beneficiaries.

In **Netherlands**, the area of crops is 1.8 million ha with an average size per holding 27.4 ha. The exact percentage of crop output corresponds to 54.9% of the total. The labor force is 146,000 people. The total amount of direct payments is almost 806 million EUR which is distributed to 49,880 beneficiaries.

In **Belgium**, the crop output holds almost half of the national agriculture output (49.1%). The holdings are satisfactorily large with an average size of 34.6 ha, while the whole crop production area is 1.3 million ha. Belgium receives 552.4 million EUR as direct payments for 35 thousand beneficiaries. The labor force in farming is 57,000 people.

The crop output in **Poland** represents 52.5% of the total agricultural output. The crop production area is 14.4 million ha with an average size per holding 10.1 ha. The labor force is 1.9 million people and constitutes the highest number between EU countries. The number of direct payments beneficiaries is also in the top positions between EU members, particularly in the third place and corresponds to 1,135,270 people. The amount of direct payments is 2.9 billion EUR.

Among the Central European countries, **Luxembourg** has the lowest rate in terms of crop output at 45.6%. It also has one of the smallest crop areas in the EU (131,380 ha). However, the average size per holding is 63 ha. Labor force in farming is 4 thousand people. The total direct payments account 33.1 million EUR which are distributed to only 1,920 beneficiaries.

In **Austria**, the crop output accounts for 47.3% of the total agricultural output. The total crop areas are 2.7 million ha. The average size per holding is 19.4 ha and the amount of people who work in farming 120,000. The total direct payments are 695.5 million EUR and they are distributed to 110,250 beneficiaries.

As it is mentioned above, Hungary and Czech Republic hold high rates of crop output among central European countries (64.4% and 61.4% respectively).

In **Hungary**, the crop area is 5.3 million ha and the average size per holding only 9.5 ha. The labor force is 442,000 people. Direct payments are almost 1.3 billion EUR and the beneficiaries of aids reach the number of 174.8 thousand people.

In **Czech Republic**, the total crop production area is 3.5 million ha, while the average size per holding is 133 ha corresponding to the highest among EU countries. The labor force is 105,000 people. The beneficiaries of direct payments are 284,600 and the amount of aids reaches 878.7 million EUR.

Slovakia and Slovenia have similar rates in crop output which correspond almost to 57%. In particular, the crop output for **Slovakia** is 57.4% of the total agricultural output. The crop production area is 1.91 million ha, the average size per holding 80.7 ha and the labor force consists of 49,000 people. Direct payments amount 371.5 million EUR, while the beneficiaries of aids are 17 thousand.

In **Slovenia**, crop output represents the 57.9% of the total agricultural output. The total crop area amounts to 476,860 ha with an average size per holding 6.7 ha. The labor force is 81,000 people. The sum of direct payments is at about 140.2 million EUR and the beneficiaries of aids 56,720 people.

In Northern Europe the countries have the lowest rates in crop production rates. More specifically, the total crop output in **Ireland** is 24.9% of the total agricultural output. The crop area is almost 4.4 million ha and the average size per holding 35.5 ha. The labor force is 164,000 people. Direct payments reach 1.2 billion EUR, while the beneficiaries are 124.6 thousand.

In **Finland** the crop output reaches the 38.1% of the total and the farming labor force 79,000 people. The crop production area is 2.27 million ha with an average size per holding at 42 ha. The amount of 519.2 million EUR direct payments is distributed to 57,070 beneficiaries.

The crop output in **Denmark** holds the 36.4% of the total agricultural output. The total crop production area account 2.6 million ha and the average size per holding is one of the highest in the EU (67.5 ha). The labor force is 55,000 people. The amount of direct payments reaches almost 917 million EUR and is distributed to 44,270 beneficiaries.

The highest crop output rate between northern countries is held by **Latvia**, which is 65.7%. Regarding the rest crop output indicators, the total crop production area is almost 1.9 million ha, the average size per holding 23 ha and the labor force 77,000 people. The total amount of direct payments is almost 143.8 million EUR and the beneficiaries of aids reach the number of 615,300 people.

In **Sweden**, almost half of the total agricultural output corresponds to crop output (51.5%). The crops reach 3.02 million ha and the average size per holding is 45.2 ha. The labor force is 60,000 people. Direct payments amount 679.5 million EUR which are distributed to 63,140 beneficiaries.

The **Estonian** crop output holds 57.5% of the total one. The crop area is 994 thousand ha with an average size per holding 49.9 ha. The labor force is 20,000 people. The amount of direct payments is 99.1 million EUR and the beneficiaries of aids 170,900 people.

In Eastern Europe, the countries hold some of the highest proportions in crop output between EU countries. Firstly, **Bulgaria** is at the second position in crop production, following Greece, with a proportion of 72.3%. In Bulgaria, the labor force consists of 276,000 people. The crop production area is 5.01 million ha with an average size per holding 18.3 ha. The total direct payments are 578.4 million EUR and are received by almost 90.5 thousand beneficiaries.

The **Romanian** crop output is 70.2% of the total. The crops reach 13.1 million ha, while the average size per holding is 3.6 ha, one of the lowest after Malta and Cyprus. However, Romania has one of the highest labor forces in farming (1.3 million people) as well as the highest number in the EU in terms of direct payments beneficiaries (1,186,290 people). The total amount of direct payments corresponds to 1.26 billion EUR.

Finally, in **Croatia**, the 60.8% of total agricultural output corresponds to crop output. The crop area is 1.5 million ha, the average size per holding 10 ha and the labor force 192,000 people. Direct payments reach 93.2 million EUR and are distributed to 92,640 beneficiaries.

Basic figures on crops, farmers and direct payments

Country	% Crop production (2015)	Average size per holding (ha)	UAA in ha (2013)	Crops*1000 ha (2015)	Laborforce 2013 (persons)	Laborforce 2015 (AWUs)	Direct Payments (2014) €*1000	Beneficiaries (2014) Number*1000
Belgium	49,1%	34,6	1.307.900	1.330,88	74.830	57.000	552.432	35,22
Bulgaria	72,3%	18,3	4.650.940	5.011,49	557.670	276.000	578.394	90,49
CzechRepublic	61,4%	133	3.491.470	3.493,72	132.130	105.000	878.683	28,46
Denmark	36,4%	67,5	2.619.340	2.632,95	80.970	55.000	916.931	44,27
Germany	52,2%	58,6	16.699.580	16.730,70	706.260	496.000	5.101.254	320,29
Estonia	57,5%	49,9	957.510	993,60	44.220	20.000	99.063	17,09
Ireland	24,9%	35,5	4.959.450	4.429,14	269.510	164.000	1.227.716	124,57
Greece	73,3%	6,8	4.856.780	4.869,61	1.238.490	442.000	2.246.414	709,27
Spain	62,5%	24,1	23.300.220	23.897,14	1.782.690	819.000	5.110.443	869,98
France	62,8%	58,7	27.739.430	29.115,25	907.080	768.000	7.781.822	358,23
Croatia	60,8%	10	1.571.200	1.537,63	388.370	192.000	93.202	92,64
Italy	65,6%	12	12.098.890	12.648,08	2.139.060	1.120.000	3.910.367	1.163,69
Cyprus	51,1%	3,1	109.330	126,47	77.390	24.000	51.667	33,22
Latvia	65,7%	23	1.877.720	1.884,80	173.920	77.000	143.763	61,53
Lithuania	64,7%	16,7	2.861.250	3.005,96	297.950	151.000	375.849	148,5
Luxembourg	45,6%	63	131.040	131,38	4.950	4.000	33.090	1,92
Hungary	64,4%	9,5	4.656.520	5.346,45	1.059.940	442.000	1.287.607	174,87
Malta	44,1%	1,2	10.880	11,69	14.870	5.000	5.274	6,07
Netherlands	54,9%	27,4	1.847.570	1.845,75	193.140	146.000	805.800	49,88
Austria	47,3%	19,4	2.726.890	2.720,40	337.580	120.000	695.527	110,25
Poland	52,5%	10,1	14.409.870	14.398,20	3.558.710	1.937.000	2.982.331	1.135,27
Portugal	58,2%	13,8	3.641.590	3.699,98	626.390	256.000	634.863	173,31
Romania	70,2%	3,6	13.055.850	13.835,47	6.577.930	1.293.000	1.259.549	1.186,29
Slovenia	57,9%	6,7	485.760	476,86	200.630	81.000	140.206	56,72
Slovakia	57,4%	80,7	1.901.610	1.921,56	80.020	49.000	371.546	17,01
Finland	38,1%	42	2.257.630	2.273,30	120.020	79.000	519.262	57,07
Sweden	51,5%	45,2	3.035.920	3.028,35	130.710	60.000	679.485	63,14
UK	39,9%	93,6	17.096.170	17.147,00	434.610	293.000	3.195.884	175,7

SOURCE: Eurostat

Common agricultural policy allocations 2014-2020 (in € million, current prices)

Member States	Direct payments	Rural development	Total CAP budget
Belgium	3 603	648	4 251
Bulgaria	5 106	2 367	7 472
Czech Republic	5 985	2 306	8 291
Denmark	6 044	919	6 963
Germany	34 534	9 446	43 980
Estonia	839	823	1 663
Ireland	8 507	2 191	10 697
Greece	14 808	4 718	19 526
Spain	34 634	8 297	42 931
France	51 354	11 385	62 739
Croatia	1 482	2 026	3 508
Italy	26 850	10 444	37 294
Cyprus	351	132	484
Latvia	1 452	1 076	2 527
Lithuania	3 104	1 613	4 717
Luxembourg	234	101	335
Hungary	8 932	3 431	12 362
Malta	37	97	134
Netherlands	5 223	765	5 988
Austria	4 850	3 938	8 787
Poland	23 313	8 698	32 010
Portugal	4 105	4 058	8 163
Romania	11 638	8 128	19 766
Slovenia	960	838	1 797
Slovakia	3 016	1 560	4 576
Finland	3 662	2 380	6 042
Sweden	4 866	1 764	6 630
UK	22 283	5 200	27 483

SOURCE: European Commission – DG Budget

In the EU the most frequent *collective entities* in the agricultural sector are agricultural cooperatives, farmers' unions, national and regional federations and agricultural chambers which mainly act as a liaison between them and public authorities, Ministries, chambers in different sectors, European authorities etc.

The level of organization of these entities among the EU countries is varied. Indicatively, French and Italian cooperatives have a strong presence in Europe, although, in some European countries the degree of farmers' organization is still at a low level e.g. Greece and Romania.

More analytically, the level of organization of the agricultural sector in **France**, as mentioned above, is one of the highest in the EU. In 2012, the 75% of French farmers were members of agricultural cooperatives, reaching a total of 2,500. Producers Organizations counted 266 members, out of which 205 implemented

Operational Programs. There are also cooperatives societies in the sectors of tobacco, banana, potatoes and hops. The French cooperatives are also organized at a higher level forming Federations of Cooperatives, National Unions of sectoral Cooperatives, Regional and Interregional Cooperatives, Assemblies of Agricultural Cooperatives etc. In organic farming the farmers are also organized in the National Federation of Organic Farming and in the National Union of Organic Companies.

The **Italian** farmers are organized in cooperatives, Producers Organizations, regional federations, provincial unions and products federations. In particular, according to LegaCoop (Cooperative Federation) by the end of 2013, there were 5,100 agricultural cooperatives. In addition in 2012 there were 276 recognised Producers Organizations, while there were 13 recognized Producers Organization Associations (POA). There was also one Producers' Group. The Italian Farmers' Confederation⁴⁰ (CIA) is one of the largest European agricultural professional organisation with approximately 900,000 directly registered growers and farmers. There are also women's and young farmers' associations. Amongst them is the Association of Young Agriculture Entrepreneurs which collaborates closely with the Italian Farmers' Confederation (CIA).

Spain was the member of the EU which in 2011 had the highest number of Producers Organizations (POs) totaling 595 members. 457 of them implemented Operational Programmes (OP)⁴¹. Approximately the 90% of POs had fewer than 500 members. Nevertheless, there were 30 POs with more than 1,000 members⁴². There is also a Spanish Wine Federation⁴³ representing the winery industry (grouping 800 wineries). Furthermore, in 2013 the Agri – Food Cooperatives represented a considerable number of members⁴⁴ (3,844 cooperatives). The Federation of Associations of Producers and Exporters of fruits, vegetables flowers and live plants is also established which is a private, non – profit industry based organization⁴⁵.

In the **United Kingdom** the level of farmers' organization is high. In particular farmers are organized in farmers' unions, national and regional associations, federations etc.⁴⁶. Furthermore, farmers are also organized in Producers Organizations (POs). According to the Evaluation Report of the UK's National Strategy for Operational Programs in the fruits and vegetables sector in 2011, some 1,195 UK growers were members of Producer Organizations which represented the 31% of a population of 3,864 horticultural growers⁴⁷. Furthermore, in each county of the UK there are producers' associations in all types of agricultural products.

In **Greece** farmers are organized in collective entities in order to improve their position in the global and national markets. The main scheme in which Greek farmers participate is Agricultural Cooperatives. As regards to the level of organization of Greek producers it is of a low level. Nonetheless after the implementation of the European Regulation for establishing a common organization of agricultural markets for certain agricultural products, Greek farmers started to establish Producer Organizations (POs) specifically in sectors of fruits and vegetables, olive oil products and wine. Olive oil and table olive sectors have been given extra funding in POs schemes in order to be further supported. POs operate as clearly defined parts of other legal entities such as Agricultural Cooperatives, SAs etc. There are also recognized Interbranch Organizations, Agricultural Trade Unions and Trade Organizations.

⁴⁰<http://www.cia.it/>

⁴¹https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/fruit-and-vegetables/country-files/es/evaluation-report-of-national-strategy-2012-main-es_en.pdf

⁴²<http://www.freshplaza.com/article/151019/Spain-Producer-Organizations-market-half-of-all-fruit-and-veg>

⁴³http://www.fev.es/v_portal/apartados/apartado.asp?te=66

⁴⁴http://www.agro-alimentarias.coop/5/uk/5_1_1.php

⁴⁵<http://www.fepex.es/inicio.aspx>

⁴⁶<http://www.nfuonline.com/home/> , <http://britishgrowers.org/> , <http://www.gaj.org.uk/> , <http://www.tfa.org.uk/>

⁴⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/fruit-and-vegetables/country-files/uk/evaluation-report-of-national-strategy-2012-uk_en.pdf

The **Lithuanian** Farmers' Union was established in 1919. Furthermore, the Association of Agricultural Companies was established in 1992 whose members were agricultural enterprises. In Lithuania also operates an Association of Agricultural Cooperatives. Furthermore, the Agricultural Chamber maintains a very close collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture. Its main goal is to maintain close ties between the Ministry, farmers and their organizations⁴⁸. The Lithuanian professional organization for organic producers and other supporters of organic agriculture is represented by Association of Organic Agriculture. There is also a Lithuanian Association of Organic Farms.

Belgian farmers are mostly associated in agricultural chambers. There are also farmers unions for supporting their members. In addition by the end of 2010, in Flanders there were four Unions of Producers Organizations (UPOs) and seven independent Producers Organizations⁴⁹. In Wallonia, in 2011, farmers established the Walloon Federation of Agriculture. There is also a Federation of Young Farmers which was founded in 2001, with over than 3,000 members. The organic farmers have also associations in all different regions of Belgium.

In **Bulgaria** farmers form cooperatives and associations. The Council of the Bulgarian Agricultural Organizations was established in view of the country's EU accession. An Association of Agricultural Producers also operates. There are agricultural cooperatives as well as organic products' associations.

In **Czech Republic** operates the Agrarian Chamber of the Czech Republic which associates the majority of entrepreneurs in agriculture, forestry and food processing industry. It provides advisory, consulting and legal services to its members. The Agrarian Chamber is the most important non-governmental agricultural professional organization and represents interests of more than 100,000 farmers, food processors, beekeepers etc. The Agricultural Association of the Czech Republic is an independent professional association. Its members are cooperatives and trade companies dealing with agriculture and related activities⁵⁰. The Association of Private Farming of the Czech Republic is an association of legal entities, i.e. different regional associations of farmers. The farmers also form Producers Organizations in the fruits and vegetables sector.

In **Denmark** every individual farmer is a member of at least one agricultural organization and of one or more producers' cooperatives. The oldest agricultural organization is the Royal Agricultural Society of Denmark (1769). In the years that followed more agricultural organizations were established. The Danish Agriculture & Food Council represents the farming and food industry of Denmark including businesses, trade and farmers' associations⁵¹. The Danish Farmers Abroad is an association of large international agricultural companies, suppliers of agricultural equipment and production means and individuals with a special interest in international agricultural commerce⁵². Danish farmers also participate in Producers Organizations in the fruits and vegetables sector.

In **Germany** the cooperative associations play an influential role in economy counting more than 20 million people. The German farmers are associated in enterprises running on a cooperative basis in the field of agriculture and food industry, including locally and internationally operating cooperatives⁵³. There are also farmers' and winegrowers' associations and organic farmers' unions.

⁴⁸<https://zum.lrv.lt/en/about-the-ministry/the-agricultural-chamber-as-helper-of-the-ministry>

⁴⁹https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/fruit-and-vegetables/country-files/be/evaluation-report-of-national-strategy-2012-main-be-fi_en.pdf

⁵⁰<http://www.dacr.cz/agricultural-association-of-the-czech-republic/>

⁵¹<http://www.agricultureandfood.dk/about-us/fokus>

⁵²<http://www.danishfarmersabroad.dk/english-danish-farmers-abroad/>

⁵³<https://germancoop.wordpress.com/>

The **Estonian** farmers are organized in agricultural cooperatives and agri – food related associations. The Central Union of Estonian Farmers also operates which mainly represents family holdings of the agricultural sector. Organizations of the agricultural and food sector are collectively organized in the Estonian Chamber of Agriculture and Commerce. The Chamber’s members are agricultural producers, processors of agricultural products and their unions and companies providing services to the agricultural sector for more than 20 years⁵⁴.

In **Ireland** farmers are organized in unions and associations. The Irish Farmers’ Association is one of the largest associations in which 75,000 farmers participate⁵⁵. The Ulster Farmers’ Union (UFU) is the largest organization representing farmers and growers in Northern Ireland⁵⁶. Furthermore, the Irish Co-operative Organization Society (ICOS) operates which is a co-operative umbrella organization that serves and promotes commercial co-operative businesses and enterprises, across multiple sections of the Irish economy⁵⁷.

In **Croatia** operates the Croatian Chamber of Agriculture with the role of coordinator organization of associations, cooperatives, family farms, business and trade in agriculture⁵⁸. Furthermore, the Croatian Associations of Cooperatives hosts different types of cooperatives including cooperatives of the agricultural sector.

The Union of **Cypriot** farmers is called “Panagrotikos Farmers’ Union” and constitutes the largest farm association in Cyprus. It is a non – profit organization and was founded in 1989 in Nicosia by agricultural producers and breeders. There are also smaller farmer’s unions in the sectors of wine, olive, dairy products, eggs, meat and vegetables⁵⁹. The organic farmers established also the Cyprus Organic Farmers Association.

According to the Ministry of Agriculture in **Latvia**, in recent years, farmers and forest owners are actively involved in operations of cooperative companies, offering their services. In the first half of 2014, there were 130 cooperative companies. The most successfully developed were cooperative companies active in milk, cereal and fruits and vegetables sectors⁶⁰. In addition, the Latvian Agricultural Cooperatives Association and Cooperatives is a non - governmental organization with members agricultural and forest cooperatives.

In **Malta** farmers are organized in agricultural cooperatives and producers organizations. Due to the small numbers in the agricultural sector the precise number of cooperatives and POs is restricted. For instance, the Maltese fruit and vegetable sector constitutes seven different entities, five classified as Producers Organizations and two as Producers’ Groups⁶¹.

According to data of the Ministry of Agriculture in **Luxembourg**, farmers compose groups as the association of agricultural holdings with exclusive management of means of production. Also the Farmers’ Unions operate providing mixed oriented services to its members.

In **Hungary** the Chamber of Agriculture is the single national chamber with legal memberships of 360,000 members. The chamber is organized in agricultural, food industry and rural development departments⁶². The

⁵⁴<http://epkk.ee/en/about/>

⁵⁵<http://www.ifa.ie/>

⁵⁶<https://www.ufuni.org/>

⁵⁷<http://www.icos.ie/>

⁵⁸<http://www.komora.hr/>

⁵⁹<http://www.biocyprus.eu/>

⁶⁰<https://www.zm.gov.lv/en/>

⁶¹https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sites/agriculture/files/fruit-and-vegetables/country-files/mt/strategy_en.pdf

⁶²<https://www.nak.hu> (presentation of Chamber)

Hungarian Farmer's Societies and the National Federation of Cooperatives as well as the Agricultural Cooperatives and Farmers Associations also operate⁶³.

In **Netherlands** the Agricultural and Horticultural Organization is a partnership of three agricultural organizations representing 50,000 farmers. There are also agricultural enterprises who are consisted by a considerable number of farmers as well as farmers' organizations and unions. In addition, in 2011 there were 17 Producers Organizations of the fruits and vegetable sector.

In **Austria** farmers are associated in agricultural chambers. There are chambers in all nine provinces. Chambers are organized at a higher level in Federal Chambers of Agriculture. The chambers are linked by an umbrella organization, the Austrian Chamber of Agriculture, which acts as a coordination body⁶⁴. The Austrian Agricultural Cluster (AAC) is an association of the leading Austrian producers of the agricultural and food sector⁶⁵.

Polish farmers are organized in trade unions and agricultural chambers. In particular, there are sixteen provincial chambers. There is also a federation of trade unions of agricultural producers which is formed by agricultural associations and their unions.

Twenty two (22) federations operate in **Portugal**. Six of them represent the agricultural sector. At a higher level there are two large confederations⁶⁶. The Confederation of Portuguese Farmers was founded in 1975. It consists of 250 organizations, from all over the country, such as regional federations and associations, wineries and unions which correspond to the main agricultural sectors of Portugal associations and cooperatives⁶⁷. There are also organizations of organic farmers. In 2011, there were 90 Producers Organizations in the sector of fruits and vegetables.

In **Romania**, the cooperative regime has totally changed during the last few years due to political rearrangements. In 2012 the National Federation of the Agriculture Romanian Producers was founded. Two years ago (2014) 276 agricultural cooperatives operated in the vegetable sector⁶⁸. Farmers are also organized in Producers Organizations.

The Chamber for Agriculture and Forestry operates in **Slovenia** as well as the members accounted for 90,244 individuals and 1,267 corporations. The membership consists of individuals, corporations (owners of agricultural land and forestry) and voluntary members of the chambers (individuals or corporations who do not fulfill the requirements of being members of the Chamber). There is also the Slovenian Farmers' Union. In addition, there is also the Cooperative Union of Slovenia which consists of agricultural, forestry and fishery cooperatives. The Union of Slovenian Organic farmers association was established in 1999 and constitutes eight regional Slovenian organic farmers associations.

The Union of Farmers and Agrarian Entrepreneurships and the Association of Land-owners and Agrarian Entrepreneurs operates in **Slovakia**. The farmers are also organised in Producers Organizations in the fruit and vegetable sector.

The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners (MTK) in **Finland** is a trade organization representing farmers, forest owners and rural entrepreneurs. It has over than 400,000 members in local agricultural producers' organizations and regional forest management associations⁶⁹. In addition there are

⁶³ Copa Cogeca Members of Hungary

⁶⁴<http://www.un.org/esa/agenda21/natlinfo/countr/austria/agriculture.pdf>

⁶⁵<http://www.advantageaustria.org/international/company/aac-austrian-agricultural-cluster-buro-wien.profile.en.html>

⁶⁶<http://www.scielo.br/pdf/resr/v53s1/0103-2003-resr-53-s1-00091.pdf>

⁶⁷<http://www.cap.pt/>

⁶⁸https://mpr.ub.uni-muenchen.de/69475/1/MPRA_paper_69475.pdf

⁶⁹https://www.mtk.fi/en_GB/

four regional councils which have a total of 70 local branches and about 11,000 members and five forestry associations which have about 20,000 members⁷⁰.

The Federation of Swedish Farmers operates in **Sweden** which is an organization of approximately 150,000 individual members. These members represent 90,000 enterprises⁷¹. Swedish cooperatives in the agricultural and forestry sector are also Federation's members. Furthermore in 2011 there were 9 recognized Producers' Organizations in the fruit and vegetable sector with 360 members in total.

⁷⁰<http://slc.fi/medlem/medlemskap-i-slc>

⁷¹<https://www.lrf.se/>

2. THIRD PARTIES

Beyond the target groups, there is a group of European authorities and bodies playing a key role in terms of producing and monitoring policy or operating as umbrella organisations and dedicated units.

2.1 DG Environment

The main task of the agricultural sector in the DG Environment is to pursue the integration of environmental concerns into the CAP, influence its developments and to ensure the continued "greening" of the policy and furthermore to decrease any adverse effects of agriculture on the environment. The tasks of the agriculture sector are among other the following:

- ☑ contribute to the development of policy on environmental issues with a link to agriculture (e.g. water, biodiversity, soil, air) and promote these issues.
- ☑ work closely with DG AGRI on the future greening of direct payments, on the development of cross-compliance and its application attached to direct CAP payments and rural development measures, and to ensure that, in the few remaining coupled common market regimes, environmental concerns are as well integrated as possible.
- ☑ contribute to the development of policy concerning environmentally friendly farming systems e.g. integrated production, organic farming.
- ☑ contribute to the formulation of indicators on the relationship between agriculture and the environment.

2.2 DG Growth

The Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs is the EC service responsible among other for delivering the EU's space policy via the two large-scale programmes Copernicus (European Earth observation satellite system) and Galileo (European global navigation satellite system), as well as research actions to spur technological innovation and economic growth.

In accordance to the role of the Commission in the field of EU's space policy, the governance of space activities in Europe is based on the cooperation between the EU, the European Space Agency (ESA), and the member countries.

The Copernicus programme provides Earth observation data and information. Through the different thematic areas it addresses (e.g. agriculture), Copernicus supports applications in a wide variety of domains. These include agriculture, biodiversity and environmental protection. Copernicus helps to assess agricultural land use, crop conditions and trends and their impacts on biodiversity and landscapes.

The provision of Copernicus services is based on the processing of data collected from Earth observation satellites. The Earth observation satellites which provide the data exploited by the Copernicus services are split into two groups of missions one of which is the Sentinels, which are currently being developed for the specific needs of the Copernicus programme.

2.3 European Court of Auditors

The European Court of Auditors (ECA) was established to audit the EU's finances. The starting point for its audit work is the EU's budget and policies, such as the Common Agricultural Policy. The ECA mission is to contribute to improving EU financial management, promote accountability and transparency and act as the independent guardian of the financial interests of the citizens of the Union. The ECA checks if the budget of the European Union has been implemented correctly and that EU funds have been raised and spent legally and in accordance with the principles of sound financial management. Moreover, the ECA warns of risks, provides assurance and offers guidance to EU policymakers on how to improve the management of public finances and ensure that Europe's citizens know how their money is being spent. The ECA's special reports set out the results of its performance and compliance audits of specific budgetary areas or management topics. The ECA selects and designs these audit tasks to be of maximum impact by considering the risks to performance or compliance, the level of income or spending involved, forthcoming developments and political and public interest.

2.4 European Environment Agency

The European Environment Agency (EEA) aims to support sustainable development by helping to achieve significant and measurable improvement in Europe's environment, through the provision of timely, targeted, relevant and reliable information to policymaking agents and the public. The Agency provides sound and independent information on the environment and constitutes a major information source for those involved in developing, adopting, implementing and evaluating environmental policy. Basic task for the EEA is to highlight the environmental concerns for the European agriculture. Particularly, EEA's work in this area focuses on the development of agri-environment indicators, thematic work on water pollution or biodiversity and the analysis of agriculture policy.

2.5 European Space Agency (ESA)

The European Space Agency (ESA) is Europe's gateway to space. Its mission is to shape the development of Europe's space capability and ensure that investment in space continues to deliver benefits to the citizens of Europe. ESA's job is to draw up the European space programme and carry it through. ESA's programmes are designed to develop satellite-based technologies and services. The role of the Sentinel missions particularly is to provide timely, continuous and independent data. Land monitoring covers a wide range of resources and associated policies. The Sentinel missions provide data support to studies and activities, and are pivotal in helping address a variety of policy areas. In particular, SENTINEL-2 provide high resolution optical image data to support Copernicus Land Monitoring studies, including the monitoring of vegetation, soil and water cover, as well as observation of inland waterways and coastal areas.

2.6 MARS Unit of the JRC

Since 1993, the activity of JRC on monitoring agriculture contributed towards a more effective and efficient management of the CAP through the provision of a broader range of technical support services to DG Agriculture and Member-State Administrations. The JRC develops methods, tools and systems for use within agricultural monitoring activities applied to Europe, and other areas of the world. Such techniques for agricultural monitoring are a key part of the Integrated Agricultural Control System (IACS) which is at the

core of CAP implementation in Europe. JRC provides methods and technical guidance in support of this implementation.

Agricultural monitoring is carried out at the JRC mainly to distinguish, identify and measure the main crop production areas in Europe, estimate production early in the year and check the validity of farmers' applications for EU subsidies. The JRC supports the implementation of the CAP and its instruments, such as the Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC) standards and the Farm Advisory System (FAS).

The JRC provides scientific and technical support for the Integrated Administration and Control System's (IACS) implementation, cross-compliance implementation and information management linked to the CAP regulations. The expertise developed within the JRC integrates research in and techniques used for carrying out statistics, image processing and interpretation (from satellite or air-borne media), geographic information system (GIS) management and web-based information technology, geomatics and GPS (orthophotos, large-scale mapping, parcel measurement), standardisation and quality control.

The JRC contributes to the standardisation processes by developing and harmonising LPIS control methods for checking CAP claims. It also provides the EU Member States with working documents, training courses and consultation services, and helps them verify the performance of their systems by implementing a Quality Assurance framework.

Earth observation is used to monitor and assess the status of, and changes in, the natural and manmade environment. Examples include the monitoring of the state and evolution of our environment, be it land, sea or air.

The JRC supports several policies within which the use of Earth observation plays a key role: the European Earth Observation Programme (Copernicus), the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS) and the Common Agricultural policy (CAP).

The ambition of the JRC is to develop a digital replica of our planet that provides globally shared access to the best available data, models, and scenarios necessary to support EU policy, public participation, and scientific research. The JRC helps set international standards for measurements from space through its in-house research and cooperation with partners, and enables the acquisition, access and storage of satellite and aerial remote sensing data.

Very High Resolution Image Acquisition for the CAP checks Programme

Since 1993, DG AGRI has promoted the use of "Controls with Remote Sensing" (CwRS) as an appropriate control system suitable to checking if aids are correctly granted. On the basis of the Council Regulation (EC) 1306/2013 and of the Commission Implementation Regulation (EC) 809/2014, 908/2014, the Commission Services are required to centralize the Satellite Remote Sensing (SRS) image acquisition. This task was transferred to DG JRC in 1998 and it is managed through a horizontal co-delegation between DG AGRI/DG JRC (via DG BUDG) to implement the yearly CAP image acquisition work programme. JRC, in agreement with DG AGRI, continues to supply Very High Resolution (VHR) SRS imagery, to the Member States' Administrations for their CwRS of area-based subsidies.

3. CURRENT AND FUTURE POLICY

In the context of the CAP, the RECAP project aims, among other, to anticipate the changes of the Omnibus regulation and furthermore and more importantly, the policy changes post 2020. Therefore a continuous follow up of policy development is crucial.

3.1 CAP legislation

The four basic Regulations of the current Common Agricultural Policy were published in December 2013. These are:

- a. *Regulation 1305/2013*, Rural Development
- b. *Regulation 1306/2013*, "Horizontal" issues such as funding and controls
- c. *Regulation 1307/2013*, Direct payments for farmers
- d. *Regulation 1308/2013*, Market measures

In order to fully implement the CAP, the European Commission services have drafted delegated acts. These delegated acts aimed at supplementing non-essential elements of the basic acts. They covered among other the following topics: "public intervention expenditure", "paying agencies and other bodies, financial management, clearance of accounts", "direct payments", "integrated administration and control system and administrative penalties applicable to direct payments and cross compliance".

Furthermore, implementing acts were adopted by the Commission to ensure that legislative acts are applied in a uniform way in all member states. The implementing acts cover among other the following topics: "paying agencies and other bodies, financial management, clearance of accounts, rules on checks, securities and transparency", "rules for direct payments" and "integrated administration and control system, rural development measures and cross compliance".

The regulation laying down the EU's multiannual financial framework for 2014-2020 was also adopted on December 2013. The amount for direct payments was specified at approximately 42 billion euro per year and in total 252 billion euro in the period 2015-2020.

3.2 Cross-compliance

Briefly, the cross-compliance scheme has the following basic characteristics. Its objective is to contribute to the development of sustainable agriculture and making the CAP more compatible with the expectations of society at large. Firstly introduced on a voluntary basis in the Agenda 2000, was further developed in the 2003 CAP reform for all the Member States (art. 3-9, Council Regulation No 1782/2003, repealed by Council Regulation (EC) No 73/2009). The rules consist of the *statutory management requirements* under Union Law and the standards for *Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition* (GAEC) of land established at national level as listed in Annex II of the Council Regulation (EU) No 1306/2013, relating among others to the following areas: environment, climate change and good agricultural condition of land. When a beneficiary does not comply with the rules on cross-compliance, an administrative penalty shall be imposed on him (art. 91-101, Council Regulation (EU) No 1306/2013).

3.3 Evolution of policy framework

The "greening" payment introduced in the 2013 CAP reform supplements cross-compliance rules. The policy framework for standards of GAEC was restructured to take into account the introduction of the greening measures. The main changes compared with the previous period are that all standards are now compulsory for recipients of direct payments and the standards were consolidated into a shorter list (Hart et al., 2016).

With the introduction of the greening payment, the maintenance of permanent grassland became a greening measure and optional standards for crop rotations have been superseded by the compulsory crop diversification greening practice. An examination of the changes in GAEC standards in four Member States found that the new cross-compliance standards led to very little change in the content of these standards under the new regime (Hart 2015).

SOURCE: DG AGRI

3.4 CAP simplification

Building on Commissioner Hogan's commitment to simplify the CAP and the four waves of simplification measures already introduced over the past year [(First wave (March 2015), Second wave (May 2015), Third wave (end 2015, beginning of 2016), Fourth wave (2016-2017)), a further series of measures have been included in the "Omnibus Regulation" published by the European Commission.

The Commission presented the legal proposal Omnibus Regulation which contains changes to the basic EU Financial Regulation and to the main EU funding Regulations (i.e. for Direct Payments, Rural Development, Common Market Organisation and Horizontal Regulation).

The measures proposed are aimed at further simplifying the policy with a view to easing the burden on and making life easier for both farmers and national authorities.

In the Direct Payments Regulation, the Commission is proposing to allow MS greater discretion in the application of the definition of an "active farmer". In effect, MS will be able to decide whether or not they wish to continue applying the existing definition of "active farmer". If applied, the system will become considerably less burdensome and will substantially ease the paperwork for both farmers and national/regional administrations.

2013 reform made a significant effort to address environmental issues within the CAP, but outcome left most stakeholders dissatisfied (Matthews, Nov.2016)

3.5 Current concerns and propositions

In a recent Special Report (October 2016), the European Court of Auditors recommended that:

- The Commission should examine as part of the impact assessment for the CAP post-2020 how to further develop its set of indicators to assess the performance of cross-compliance and how to take into account farmers' levels of compliance with the cross-compliance rules in its indicators.
- The Commission should from now on improve the sharing of the information on cross-compliance related infringements between concerned services in order to help them identify the reasons for breaches and to take appropriate measures to address them.
- For the CAP post-2020, the Commission should propose adapting the rules regarding cross-compliance on-the-spot checks. This would allow a more effective targeting of key control points.
- The Commission should analyse as part of the impact assessment for the CAP post-2020 the experience of having two systems operating with similar environmental objectives (GAEC standards and greening) with a view to promoting further synergy between them. This analysis should take into consideration criteria such as the environmental impact of the standards and the historical level of compliance by farmers.
- After the report on the performance of the CAP due by the end of 2018, the Commission should develop a methodology to measure the costs of cross-compliance.
- For the CAP post-2020, the Commission should encourage a more harmonised application of penalties at EU level by further clarifying the concepts of severity, extent, permanence, reoccurrence and intentionality.

The Danish Business Forum (Oct. 2016) proposed a revision of the cross-compliance rules in order to create greater transparency and proportionality of the regulatory framework and to minimise the risk of differing interpretations in the Member States.

The REFIT Platform has considered the issue raised by the Danish Business Forum regarding the administration of cross compliance rules in the Members States. The recommendations to the Commission addressed a call to clarify best practice under cross-compliance in order to avoid implementation that in scope is suboptimal and administratively inefficient, and requirements that are far reaching and impose excessive burdens on farmers as a result of unclear targets.

Three models are currently on the table, which respectively highlight the following. Model 1 indicates that payments should be targeted on specific objectives with a clear results orientation. Payments should be restructured within a one-pillar, programmed, multi-annual CAP, and national co-financing should be required for all CAP expenditure. Model 2 addresses that decoupled direct payments should be gradually phased out over time. Also, savings should be directed to more spending on risk management, improving competitiveness and environmental public goods and furthermore payment entitlements should be replaced by a contractual framework. Model 3 indicates that cross-compliance and the greening payment should be replaced with "conditional greening" whereby the receipt of public support would be conditional on enrolling in a basic (shallow) environmental scheme devised by the member state. Further, the allocation of budget resources should be incentive-based so that budgets are allocated to member states based on performance as well as needs (A. Matthews, Nov. 2016).

Looking at the post-2020 period, the proposed revision of the 2014-2020 Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) will prepare the ground for a subsequent MFF proposal in support of EU priorities. This is estimated to be presented by the end of 2017. With the Omnibus Regulation proposal, it appears unlikely that a major restructuring of the basic architecture of the CAP will take place in the current programming period 2014-2020. More substantial legal proposals for a post-2020 CAP could be presented in 2018, in line with the post-2020 MFF communication.

4. PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

As the paying agencies are considered the main target group, this chapter highlights the EU procurement legislative background as well as countries' specificities.

4.1 EU Public procurement legal framework

Public procurement in the European Union is subject to the EU Treaty principles of: non-discrimination; free movement of goods; freedom to provide services and freedom of establishment. In addition to these fundamental principles, some general principles of law in the procurement context have also emerged from the case law of the European Court of Justice, which are: equality of treatment; transparency; mutual recognition and proportionality.

During the last decades the EU has adopted legislation to ensure that the European public procurement market is open and competitive and that suppliers are treated equally and fairly. Generally, the rules cover aspects such as advertising of contracts, procedures for assessing company credentials, awarding the contracts and remedies (penalties) when these rules are breached. The purpose of the EU procurement rules, underpinned by the Treaty principles, is to open up the public procurement market and to ensure the free movement of supplies, services and works within the EU.

The EU rules are contained in a series of Directives that are updated from time to time. Member states have to develop national legislation (regulations) to implement the EU rules in domestic law by certain deadlines. The most recent update of the EU procurement Directives was in 2014. In particular, it was in April 2014 when the EU adopted revised public sector and utilities Directives as well as a new Directive to regulate the award of concession contracts. Member states then had 2 years to implement these in national law i.e. by April 2016. The key objectives of the new Directives were to make the current rules more simple and flexible and to contribute to growth by improving suppliers' access to the EU market. The three directives are the followings:

- **Directive 2014/23/EU** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on the award of concession contracts.
- **Directive 2014/24/EU** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on public procurement and repealing Directive 2004/18/EC
- **Directive 2014/25/EU** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on procurement by entities operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services sectors and repealing Directive 2004/17/EC

Their adoption has come as a part of a broader reform that is in progress the last years under the responsibility of the European Commission with the aim to ensure that public procurement is fair, competitive and conducive to the Single Market. This is necessary since the EU public procurement market is huge. Just to mention that every year, over 250 000 public authorities in the EU spend around 14% of GDP on the purchase of services, works and supplies. Also, public contracts falling within the scope of the European Directives represent EUR 425 billion annually or 3.4 % of the EU's GDP (2011 figures). These rules regulate the way public authorities and certain public utility operators in EU-28 purchase goods, works and services. Only in specific cases public authorities may award contracts without publishing a call for tenders,

e.g. emergencies due to unforeseeable events. As already mentioned, the Directives have to be transposed into national legislation and apply to tenders whose monetary value exceeds a certain amount (threshold), which is:

- ≥ EUR 5,225,000 for all public works contracts,
- ≥ EUR 209,000 for all supplies and services contracts,
- ≥ EUR 750,000 for public service contracts for social and other specific services,
- ≥ EUR 135,000 for public supply and service contracts in the field of defense⁷².

The public contracts with estimated value below the above mentioned thresholds are awarded according to the national legislation. Nevertheless, according to the European Commission (2006/C 179/02) “Contracting entities from Member States have to comply with the rules and principles of the EC Treaty whenever they conclude public contracts falling into the scope of that Treaty. These principles include the free movement of goods, the right of establishment, the freedom to provide services, non-discrimination and equal treatment, transparency, proportionality and mutual recognition”. Besides, the European Court of Justice has confirmed in its case-law that the Internal Market rules of the EC Treaty apply also to contracts outside the scope of the Public Procurement Directives.

The Directive 2014/24/EU, which all public authorities in EU-28 (including Paying Agencies) have to apply when awarding public contracts, foresees several types of public procurement procedure, which are also applied more or less to the Directive 2014/25/EU, as follows:

I. Open procedure (Article 27)

In open procedures any interested economic operator may submit a tender in response to a call for competition, while the minimum time limit for the receipt of tenders shall be 35 days from the date on which the contract notice was sent.

II. Restricted procedure (Article 28)

In restricted procedures any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a call for competition containing the information set out in Annex V parts B or C as the case may be by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting authority. However, only those economic operators invited to do so by the contracting authority, following its assessment of the information provided, may submit a tender. In other words, any business may ask to participate but only those who are pre-selected will be invited to submit a tender. The minimum time limit for the receipt of tenders shall be 30 days from the date on which the invitation to tender was sent.

III. Competitive procedure with negotiation (Article 29)

In competitive procedures with negotiation any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a call for competition containing the information set out in Annex V parts B and C by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting authority. Only those economic operators invited by the contracting authority, following its assessment of the information provided, may submit an initial tender, which shall be the basis for the subsequent negotiations. The contracting authorities shall negotiate with tenderers the initial and all subsequent tenders submitted by them, except for the final tenders, to improve the content thereof.

⁷² The thresholds are being revised every two years by the EC.

IV. Competitive dialogue (Article 30)

In competitive dialogues any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a contract notice by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting authority. The minimum time limit for receipt of requests to participate shall be 30 days from the date on which the contract notice was sent. Only those economic operators invited by the contracting authority, following the assessment of the information provided, may participate in the dialogue. The contract shall be awarded on the sole basis of the award criterion of the best price-quality ratio in accordance with Article 67(2). Contracting authorities shall open, with the participants selected, a dialogue in order to identify and define the means best suited to satisfying their needs. They may discuss all aspects of the procurement with the chosen participants during this dialogue.

V. Innovation partnership (Article 31)

The innovation partnership shall aim at the development of an innovative product, service or works and the subsequent purchase of the resulting supplies, services or works, provided that they correspond to the performance levels and maximum costs agreed between the contracting authorities and the participants. In other words, an innovative partnership meets the need for an innovative product, service or works that cannot be met by purchasing products, services or works already available on the market. In innovation partnerships any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a contract notice by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting authority. The contracting authority may decide to set up the innovation partnership with one partner or with several partners conducting separate research and development activities.

In conclusion, contracting authorities in the EU may apply open or restricted procedures as well as innovation partnerships. They may also apply a competitive procedure with negotiation or a competitive dialogue in certain cases. Under certain cases and circumstances contracting authorities may apply a negotiated procedure without prior publication of a call for competition. According to the Article 32, the negotiated procedure without prior publication may be used for public works contracts, public supply contracts and public service contracts in any of the following cases:

(a) where no tenders or no suitable tenders or no requests to participate or no suitable requests to participate have been submitted in response to an open procedure or a restricted procedure;

(b) where the works, supplies or services can be supplied only by a particular economic operator for any of the following reasons: (i) the aim of the procurement is the creation or acquisition of a unique work of art or artistic performance; (ii) competition is absent for technical reasons; (iii) the protection of exclusive rights, including intellectual property rights;

(c) in so far as is strictly necessary where, for reasons of extreme urgency brought about by events unforeseeable by the contracting authority, the time limits for the open or restricted procedures or competitive procedures with negotiation cannot be complied with.

Last, it is worth noting that procurement digitalization has been one more important step taken by the European Commission, as part of an effort to achieve transparent, fair, and competitive public procurement across the Single Market. The digital transformation to an e-procurement process involves initiatives developed by the European Commission and EU countries, which aim to reform aspects of the public procurement process, such as the prequalification of economic operators (European Single Procurement Document and e-Certis) and e-invoicing. Some of the measures to be adopted in this context include the use of electronic tender opportunities and tender documents (by April 2016) and full electronic means of

communication including electronic bid submission for central purchasing bodies (by April 2017). However, the most important provision has to do with the mandatory introduction of e-submission for all contracting authorities and all procurement procedures by October 2018. Concerning the Directive 2014/55/EU on electronic invoicing, this must be transposed to the national legislation of each member state before 27 November 2018.

4.2 Public procurement in the pilot countries

Although the Directives have provided a transitional period of up to 2 years (deadline in 18 April 2016) for the EU-28 member states to comply with, finally only 7 member states had succeed, by the end of May 2016, in transposing the new EU directives on public procurement into their national legal order. As a result, the Commission has delivered a formal request to Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Cyprus, Estonia, Ireland, Greece, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Finland, Spain and Sweden, to transpose in full one or more of the three directives on public procurement and concessions (Directives 2014/23/EC, 2014/24/EC, 2014/25/EC) into national law. However there was little progress over the next period. By early December 2016 there have been still numerous EU member states that had failed to meet the deadline for transposing public procurement and concessions rules into national legislation. As a result, the European Commission is to send a second written warning to 15 member states, as they have yet to fully transpose one or more of the three Directives on public procurement and concessions adopted in 2014 into national law or have failed to report the transposition to Brussels. The countries identified by the Commission were: Austria (3 Directives), Belgium (3), Bulgaria (1), Croatia (3), Cyprus (2), Estonia (3), Finland (3), Ireland (1), Latvia (3), Lithuania (3), Luxembourg (3), Portugal (3), Slovenia (1), Spain (3) and Sweden (3).⁷³

In the same context, the European Commission has drafted a group of six indicators (One Bidder, No calls for Bids, Aggregation, Award Criteria, Decision Speed, Reporting Problems)⁷⁴ in order to monitor the performance of each member state on key aspects of public procurement. The following map shows the overall performance per country as a weighted average of all the performance indicators (Triple weight is given to most important indicators: One Bidder and No Calls for Bids).

⁷³ Press Release "Procurement Directives: second warning for 15 EU states", 8/12/2016, <http://www.euwid-recycling.com/>

⁷⁴ All indicators are based on notices published in the Tenders Electronic Daily (TED) database under the general, sectoral, and defence procurement directives.

EU-28 performance on key aspects of public procurement

SOURCE: European Commission, 2016

UNITED KINGDOM

The UK has a largely centralised procurement system that presents some unique characteristics compared to other EU countries. Furthermore, it makes a comparatively high use of restricted and competitive dialogue procedures, and a relative smaller use of the open procedure, which is more widespread in continental Europe.⁷⁵

The UK's high use of restricted procedures makes it an outlier as it is the only member state in which open procedures are not used for the majority of contracts. This is made even more notable by the fact that elsewhere in the EU, the use of restricted tenders is in decline. UK public bodies favour restricted procedures because they limit the number of tenderers per contract, thus reducing the cost of evaluating bids, as well as the cost of bidding for the candidates. However, the two-stage tendering process takes longer than an open procedure, and can be more restrictive for potential suppliers to comply with, due to the quality of tender submissions required. The UK's administrative structure also impacts its procurement system, with unique legal regimes for England, Wales and Northern Ireland on the one hand, and Scotland on the other one. Implementation of procurement is even more decentralised, with national institutions in Wales and Northern Ireland as well.⁷⁶

⁷⁵ PwC, Ecorys, London Economics (2011), *Public procurement in Europe: Cost and Effectiveness*.

⁷⁶ European Commission, *Public procurement – Study on administrative capacity in the EU – United Kingdom Country Profile*, 2016.

Like many member states, the UK procurement system has undergone a wave of reforms, the second to be launched in the past five years. The goal of these reforms was to increase standardisation and centralisation of procurement at the UK level, and to improve capacity at all levels.

In this context, in England, Wales and Northern Ireland, the Public Contracts Regulation 2015⁷⁷ came into force in 26 February 2015 (SI 2015 No. 102), which transposes the ‘classical’ procurement directive 2014/24/EU and implements UK rules. For utilities, which means the contracting entities (“utilities”) operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services sectors, the implementation of the Utilities Contracts Regulations 2016 (SI 2016 No. 274) took effect from 18 April 2016. These Regulations do not extend to Scotland, where separate, but similar Regulations came into effect in April 2016. Any authority entering into a contract that is to be carried out in Scotland would need to consider the application of the Scottish Regulations.

The Public Contracts Regulations 2015 and the Utilities Contracts Regulations 2016 are supplemented by the Public Procurement (Amendments, Repeals and Revocations) Regulations 2016 (SI 2016 No. 275) which makes consequential amendments to other legislation, including the Public Services (Social Value) Act 2012.

It has to be stressed that the UK is an EU leader in e-procurement with one of the highest uptake rates of any EU member state, despite the fact that neither e-notification nor e-submission is mandatory. More than 50% of all contracts are currently published online, with the exception of sensitive military contracts. Estimates of the levels of e-submission uptake place the UK in the range between 50% and 75%, with approximately 75% of central government bodies carrying out procurement fully electronically. The Government procurement portal includes a searchable database of contract notices called Contracts Finder, as well as a pipeline to allow potential bidders to prepare for up-coming procurements. It also hosts a Spend Analysis Tool with regularly updated information on procurement organised by category and supplier. In addition to the UK-wide site, there are the Public Contracts Scotland, Sell2Wales and eSourcing NI sites providing similar data for Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland respectively.⁷⁸

In the same context, in May 2013 the government published the ‘Cloud First’ policy, for public sector IT, according to which purchases through the cloud should be the first option considered by public sector buyers of IT products and services. In other words, when procuring new or existing services, public sector organisations should consider and fully evaluate potential cloud solutions first – before they consider any other option. This approach is mandated to central government and strongly recommended to the wider public sector. Departments will remain free to choose an alternative to the cloud if they can demonstrate that it offers better value for money.⁷⁹

Last, at institutional level the primary procurement institution for England, Wales and N. Ireland is the “Efficiency and Reform Group” (ERG), which is responsible for improving operational efficiency government-wide. ERG plays several roles, including in transposing EU Directives, handling infraction cases, supervising procurement activity for value, and providing guidance and training for contracting authorities. As such, it is the primary body in charge for procurement policy. However, the obligations and liabilities on specific procurement procedures remain with the contracting authority. In Scotland, the “Scottish Procurement and Commercial Directorate (SPD)” plays a comparable role. Contracting authorities, on the other hand, bear the liability for the fulfillment of obligations related to public procurement procedures. The Crown Commercial Service (CCS) acts as one of the central purchasing bodies, and is designed to increase UK’s value for money

⁷⁷The Public Contracts Regulations 2015, available at: http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2015/102/pdfs/ukxi_20150102_en.pdf

⁷⁸ European Commission, *Public procurement – Study on administrative capacity in the EU – United Kingdom Country Profile*, 2016.

⁷⁹ Cabinet Office, press release “Government adopts ‘Cloud First’ policy for public sector IT”, 5 May 2013

by aggregating purchasing power, providing advice and support to other government departments, and having the lead on procurement policy on behalf of the UK government. In addition to the CCS, several administrations are acting as central purchasing bodies at regional and local levels.

GREECE

The legal regime of public procurement in Greece is based on the fundamental principles and procedures of EU public procurement legislation, as the latter has been defined by the European Commission and interpreted by the EU Court of Justice. However, until very recently the Greek Public procurement legislation consisted of a multi-layered structure of legal acts (as many as 400 laws, regulations, and presidential decrees), depending on the contracting authority (central government, wider public sector, decentralized authorities, self-government and other entities) and the estimated value of the contracts (either below or above the EU thresholds).

As part of the coordinated response effort to address the economic crisis, the Greek government has undertaken a major process of structural reforms in order to increase efficiency of the public sector and competitiveness of the national economy. In this context, public procurement features prominently among the functions to be reformed, having been identified by the OECD as one of the top drivers of administrative costs. During recent years substantial progress has been made in consolidating and rationalising responsibilities, including through the establishment of the “Single Public Procurement Independent Authority” (Law 4013/2011), which is responsible for a wide range of policy, executive and oversight functions.

In addition, the procurement system features prominently in a government-wide push to increase transparency and combat corruption. This includes the rapid adoption of e-procurement and online reporting tools, which have substantially increased the efficiency, openness, and ease of oversight of the system. Consequently, the Greek e-procurement system is relatively advanced, offering a range of services to awarding authorities and bidders. It applies to public supplies and public services contracts but it does not apply yet to public works. The central portal, known as “Prometheus”, contains links to all the key platforms, as well as training and guidance material, legal material, and statistical reports. The key e-procurement platform is the “National Electronic Public Procurement System” (ESIDIS), which offers e-notification, e-access, and e-submission. A blanket government mandate for all three categories was phased in for goods, services and works over the course of 2014 for all contracts with estimated value over EUR 60,000. More precisely, it is about an integrated electronic platform, which has to be used in all the stages of public contracts from the preparation and publication of the notice of tender and the submission of tenders from potential contractors until the evaluation and the award of a contract. For the post awarding procedure, the Greek Government has established electronic tools, such as e-auction, e-catalogue, e-ordering, e-payment and e-archiving. Use of these tools is not mandatory to this date. Prometheus also hosts links to the “Central Electronic Registry for Public Procurement” (KIMDIS), which serves as a transparency register. All procurement notices worth EUR 1,000 and above must be published by the contracting authorities/entities on this platform. The data which are published to the Register refer to all of the stages of public contracts. Furthermore, there is a search engine for open public data, UltraCl@rity, which contains all Greek open Government documents, including relevant data and information on tenders and procurement procedures.

The portal was established with the objective to promote transparency among the Greek citizens and to encourage the use of public data.⁸⁰

As part of structural reforms, the Greek parliament voted in August 2016 for the Law 4412/2016, by which the new EU Directives 2014/24/EU and 2014/25/EU on public procurement have been incorporated into the national legislation. Also, the Directive 2014/23/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on the award of concession contracts has been incorporated to the Greek national legislation with the Law 4413/2016.

The Law 4412/2016 replaced the multi-layered structure of legal acts previously applied with a common legal framework, which itself is now applied to all different kind of tenders (i.e. works, services, including studies, and supplies), all kind of public entities and all contracts (i.e. above and below the EU thresholds). In other words, the Law 4412/2016 now regulates in a uniform manner the award procedures and the performance of all public supplies, services and works contracts in all areas. In particular, the provisions of the new law apply to all contracts regardless of type and estimated value, with the exception of certain regulations that apply only to specific contract categories.

According to legal experts, the objective of unifying and simplifying the national legal framework for public contracts through transposing the new reform package of the EU legislation into national law is considered to be achieved in principle. On the positive side, the new legislative initiative has introduced transparency and anti-corruption guarantees, and has placed special emphasis on forecasting and planning public contracts. It should also be noted that the participation of economic operators in calls for tenders and the performance of procurement procedures is facilitated and simplified. However, the maintenance of several provisions of the existing legislation in this field, the differentiation of regulations for certain contract categories, without this being inherently required, and the provision for issuing a multitude of administrative acts (Ministerial Decisions, Presidential Decrees, circulars) essential in order to specify several provisions of the law and achieve its full application, weaken the uniform application of the law and might give rise once again to special regimes and deviations. Besides, the Laws 4412 and 4413/2016 include significant regulations in the field of legal protection during the procurement and the execution of contract stages.⁸¹

SPAIN

In Spain, public procurement mirrors the de-centralised political system and is governed by a variety of institutions at national and regional level. While the legal system is applicable nation-wide, policy making and actual expenditure is largely carried out at sub-central level. The recently created Directorate General of Rationalisation and Procurement Centralisation (DGRCC) serves as central purchasing body and promotes efficiency in central government spending with the possibility for regions and municipalities to adhere to the system.⁸²

The current public procurement system of Spain is set out mainly in (i) “Royal Decree-Law 3/2011”, in which the Revised Text of the Law on Public Sector Contracts (hereinafter, “TRLCSP”) is approved, as amended; (ii) the “Royal Decree 1098/2001”, that develops the former public contract law but is now in force in the parts that it does not oppose to TRLCSP; (iii) and also, the “Royal Decree 817/2009”, that partially develops TRLCSP. The “31/2007 Act” provides specific rules for public procurement within the water, energy,

⁸⁰ European Commission, *Public procurement – Study on administrative capacity in the EU - Greece Country Profile*, 2016.

⁸¹ Fortsakis, Diakopoulos, Mylonogiannis & Associates (“FDMA”), *NEWSLETTER No 2 • October 2016*

⁸² European Commission, *DG Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, Study on “Strategic use of public procurement in promoting green, social and innovation policies”, Spain In-Depth Country Report*, 15/06/2016

transport, and postal services sectors. This national legislation is further developed at regional level through either regional implementation laws or implementation guidelines.

TRLCSP sets out the rules and manner of awarding public contracts, measures of legal protection, control over the procedure of awarding public procurement contracts and the competent authority for the matters regulated by the Act. The principles of freedom of access, transparency, public exposure, and equal treatment without discrimination are the underlying principles of the regulatory standards concerning public procurement. These principles appear in all stages of contracting, from the preparatory state of contracts, through to their execution.⁸³

There is no difference between selection and award procedures used for tenders above and below EU thresholds. However, time limits fixed by national legislation are narrower when the contract falls below the EU thresholds. Simplified procedures are available for two types of contracts. Firstly, negotiated procedures can be used for contracts between EUR 18,000 and EUR 60,000 for services and supplies, and from EUR 50,000 to EUR 200,000 for public works, as long as the launching of the tenders is communicated to 3 tenderers. Secondly, so-called “minor contracts” that have a duration of less than one year and a value below EUR 18,000 for services and supplies and EUR 50,000 for public works. These contracts can be awarded directly to any supplier without publication. These simplified procedures are frequently used by some regional and local authorities, for instance, 86% of public contracts awarded in Andalusia in 2011 were minor contracts.⁸⁴

Due to consecutive elections held the last period in Spain, the EU Directives have not been fully transposed into Spanish law, but parliamentary works on a new bill in this respect are very advanced during the last months of 2016. In fact, the Spanish government has already submitted to the Parliament two draft laws on public procurement, which not only introduce significant amendments to the procedures on public sector procurement, in accordance with the new EU Directives, but also form part of the reformist agenda that the government has been deploying since 2012 and which, in regard to the public administration, seeks to improve the functioning and more effective use of public resources.⁸⁵ In this context, reforms have been implemented to strengthen the monitoring and control of public contracts to promote transparency and reduce irregularities, fraud, and corruption. Since the deadline for the transposition of the EU Directives has already expired, the Spanish government will request their passage under the fast-track procedure.

In conclusion, substantial efforts are underway to improve the centralisation and harmonisation of the system to reduce the costs of its current dispersed nature. Besides, the new legislation on public procurement includes a commitment to electronic means, facilitates access to SMEs, increases transparency and places greater emphasis on environmental, social and innovative policies.

Last, the use of e-procurement in Spain remains, so far, quite limited. The one area in which utilization is more advanced is e-publication of contract notices through individual procurement profiles for each administration, which was made mandatory for all contracting authorities as part of the 2011 reforms. E-submission of bids is not mandatory and thus not usually offered by contracting authorities. Qualified national digital signatures (DNI-e) are currently being assigned to Spanish enterprises for use in e-submission, but are not available to foreign suppliers. The State Public Procurement Platform (PLACE) hosts a central registry for contracting authorities to post tenders launched in the country, and which automatically sends that information to the State Official Journal (BOE) and to the EU Official Journal. However, usage of

⁸³ “A few questions about Implementation of the EU public procurement directives”, 2/6/2016. www.dentons.com

⁸⁴ European Commission, *Public procurement – Study on administrative capacity in the EU - Spain Country Profile*, 2016.

⁸⁵ Press article “GOVERNMENT STEPS UP FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT”, <http://www.theleader.info/>, 29/11/2016

the platform is limited due in part to the fact that several public agencies and regional authorities operate their own competing procurement platforms often via private IT providers. Currently, authorities in Aragon, Cantabria and Madrid are working with the Ministry of Finance to integrate their platforms with the central portal to share notices and bidder registries. The Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations is currently preparing additional e-procurement integration efforts in order to concentrate the publication of tenders on a unique public procurement platform for the public sector. Because contracting authorities are not required to report e-procurement data, monitoring is necessarily limited. Ministry of Finance and Public Administrations reporting is limited to data on the activities of the national e-procurement platform only.⁸⁶

LITHUANIA

In Lithuania procurement accounts for roughly a third of the national budget, and is primarily conducted by sub-national contracting authorities with the national procurement supervising body operating a strong reporting system to monitor their activities. As a result, updated data on the planning and implementation of tender procedures is regularly published, making Lithuanian public procurement particularly transparent. Nevertheless, problems persist in practice, especially when it comes to reducing the number of irregularities and controlling the correct application of public procurement legislation.⁸⁷

Public procurement in the country is carried out in accordance with the rules set out in the “Law on public Procurement”. The Law establishes the procedure, rights, obligations, and responsibility of entities which engage in procurement, in addition to the procedure for exercising control of public procurement, and settling disputes. The Law set into force on the 13 August 1996, and was subsequently amended in order to meet the requirements of the EU, the European Parliament and Council Directives 2004/17/EC and 2004/18/EC from March 31, 2004 regarding public procurement and its procedures. Several legal acts provide more specific regulations on the provisions of the law, offering standard contract documents, giving recommendations to contracting authorities and promoting certain trends such as centralised public procurement. So far (i.e. December 2016), Lithuania has yet to transpose the three EU Directives on public procurement and concessions adopted in 2014.

According to the Law of Public Procurement, contracting authority is: any state or local authority; any association of state or local authorities and/or of public or private legal persons referred meeting the conditions specified below; any legal persons engaged in water, energy, transport or telecommunication activity referred to in sub-paragraphs 2-4 of paragraph 1 of Article 70 of the Law on public procurement. Any other public or private legal person is considered contracting authority and therefore must follow the provisions set forth in the Law, if all or part of its activities is intended to meet the needs of general interest, not having an industrial or commercial character, and the company itself meets certain conditions.

Contracting authorities can select among five available types of procedure: open procedure; restricted procedure; competitive dialogue; negotiated procedure (with or without publication of a contract notice); design contest. Besides, the law introduces two levels below EU thresholds. Contracts below EUR 3,000 in value are largely free of regulation, including mandatory contract notification. For contracts above this value, but below EUR 58,000 for supplies and services and EUR 145,000 for works, simplified procedures can be applied. Above these limits, but below the EU thresholds, individual contracting authorities have to set up their own implementation rules and publish them in the Central Public Procurement Information System

⁸⁶ European Commission, *Public procurement – Study on administrative capacity in the EU - Spain Country Profile*, 2016.

⁸⁷ European Commission, *Public procurement – Study on administrative capacity in the EU – Lithuania Country Profile*, 2016.

(CVP IS). These rules can be developed on the basis of the standard rules prepared by the Public Procurement Office (PPO) and have to be compliant with the requirements of the Law on contract notices, verification of tenderers' qualification, technical specifications, tender evaluation, and terms for submitting bids. In addition, contracting authorities must define and publish an annual procurement plan estimating the value of public procurement for the coming year.⁸⁸

The "CVP IS" is Lithuania's e-procurement one-stop-shop, launched by the PPO in 2008 to be used by all contracting authorities and bidders. The CVP IS covers all the pre-awarding phases of the public procurement process: e-notification, e-access, e-submission and e-awarding. E-notification and e-access have been mandatory for all contracting authorities since 2009, even for low value tenders, while e-submission is required for at least 50% of the total value of public procurement of each contracting authority. The number of users of CVP IS is constantly growing. This includes 97% of all contracting authorities and more than 15,000 suppliers, including nearly 600 foreign companies. E-procurement uptake reached approximately 90% of total procurement in 2013, making Lithuania one of the most advanced countries in the EU in this area.

Public procurement is supervised by the "Public Procurement Office", a body operating under the Ministry of Economy. Public Procurement Office drafts and adopts legal acts regulating procurement, carries out prevention of violations, controls compliance of contracting authorities with the requirements of legal acts and ensures appropriate planning of procurement and performance of public contracts. It also examines administrative cases within the limits of its competence, provides methodological assistance on implementation of the Law on Public Procurement and organizes the training in public procurement. The institutional system is completed with the "Competition Council" and the "Central Purchasing Organisation" (CPO). The Competition Council investigates possible anti-competitive practices from both contracting authorities and bidders. It reports its findings to the PPO and can impose fines as well as refer cases to the courts in case of competition law infringements related to public procurement. In order to optimise tasks and avoid possible redundancies, the PPO and the Competition Council agreed in 2011 on a separation of their functions: the PPO reviews compliance with public procurement rules, the Competition Council ensures compliance with competition regulation. The CPO conducts centralised procurement on behalf of contracting authorities, including the central administration and its territorial branches, as well as local authorities. It aims to ensure the rational, transparent and efficient use of public funds and administrative resources through centralised public procurement. It negotiates framework agreements for a wide range of products, services and public works, which contracting authorities can browse and order online using an e-catalogue.

Finally, notices on public procurement (prior information notices, contract notices, contract award notices, and notices of the results of a design contest) are published in the Official Journal of the European Union and announced in the Central Portal of Public Procurement.⁸⁹

⁸⁸ European Commission, *Public procurement – Study on administrative capacity in the EU – Lithuania Country Profile*, 2016.

⁸⁹ GencsValters Law Firm, Latvia, <http://baltic-lawfirm.eu/en/law-firm.html>

SERBIA

The Serbian legal framework on public procurement includes the Public Procurement Law (Official Gazette of RS No. 124/2012, 14/2015 and 68/2015) (hereinafter, the “PPL”) and various by-laws regulating, in more detail, specific aspects of public procurement.

The basic principles in the public procurement system of Serbia are (i) principle of efficiency and cost-effectiveness, (ii) principle of ensuring competition, (iii) principle of transparency in a public procurement procedure, (iv) principle of equality of bidders, and (v) principle of environmental protection and ensuring energy efficiency.

The PPL provides for eight different types of public procurement procedures: Open procedure; restricted procedure; qualification procedure; negotiated procedure with invitation to bid; negotiated procedure without invitation to bid; competitive dialogue; design contest and low-value public procurement procedure. Also, the PPL provides for two main criteria for the contract awarding (i) economically most advantageous bid, or (ii) lowest price offered. When the estimated value of public procurement exceeds 250,000,000 RSD (approximately 203,000 EUR as on 30 April 2016) for goods and services, or 500,000,000 RSD (approximately 406,000 EUR as on 30 April 2016) for works, the contracting authority is obliged to publish the public procurement notice in a foreign language commonly used in international trade in the field of public procurement. The contracting authorities are not obliged to apply the provisions of the PPL in cases where the procurement of goods, services and works whose estimated individual value and total value on the annual level is lower than 500,000 RSD (approximately 4,060 EUR as on 30 April 2016).

Even though the Republic of Serbia is not a Member State of the European Union, it aims to have the public procurement system harmonised with the EU legal framework. This being said, the PPL, as amended in 2015, is harmonised with the latest EU Directives in this field – Directive 2014/24/EU on public procurement, Directive 2014/23/EC on the award of concession contracts, and Directive 2014/25/EC on procurement by entities operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services sectors.⁹⁰

In 2003 Serbia was identified as a potential candidate for EU membership, whereas in 2008 a European partnership for Serbia was adopted, setting out priorities for the country's membership application. Then, in March 2012 Serbia was granted EU candidate status and in the begging of 2014 Serbia's accession negotiations formally started. Regarding Chapter 5: “Public procurement” and according to the European Commission *“Serbia is moderately prepared in this area, which is particularly vulnerable to corruption. Further efforts are needed to prevent corruption from occurring during the procurement cycle. Some progress has been made in the past year, notably through the adoption of secondary legislation and a further increase in competition in tender procedures. Significant efforts are needed across the board to further improve competition, efficiency and transparency in public tenders.”*⁹¹

In general, the national legal framework on public procurement is largely aligned with the *acquis communautaire* on classical and utilities procurement, while several implementing by-laws were adopted so far. However, additional measures are needed to further strengthen the capacity of different public procurement stakeholders to fight corruption, to reduce the number of irregularities and to encourage the use of the ‘most economically advantageous tender’ selection criterion.

⁹⁰ Public Procurement 2016-Serbia, *International Comparative Legal Guides*, <http://www.iclg.co.uk/>

⁹¹ 2016 Communication on EU Enlargement Policy, Serbia 2016 Report, European Commission, Brussels, 9.11.2016 SWD(2016) 361 final.

At an institutional level, the Public Procurement Office (PPO) supervises the implementation of the law on public procurement. The PPO was established as an independent governmental agency with the mandate to establish a sound procurement system, and prepare procedures that would ensure that public funds are spent in an efficient and transparent way, thus complementing government's overall drive in containing corruption. The aim of the PPO is to promote knowledge and understanding of Public Procurement Law.

5. ICT PENETRATION

The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) is a composite index developed by the European Commission (DG CNECT) to assess the development of EU countries towards a digital economy and society. It aggregates a set of relevant indicators structured around 5 dimensions: Connectivity, Human Capital, Use of Internet, Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services.

The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) is a composite index that summarises relevant indicators on Europe's digital performance and tracks the evolution of EU Member States in digital competitiveness.

Denmark, the Netherlands, Sweden, and Finland have the most advanced digital economies in the EU followed by Belgium, the UK and Estonia.

Romania, Bulgaria, Greece and Italy are at the bottom of the list.

The five dimensions of the DESI

1 Connectivity	Fixed Broadband, Mobile Broadband, Broadband speed, and Affordability
2 Human Capital	Basic Skills and Usage, Advanced skills and Development
3 Use of Internet	Content, Communication and Transactions on line
4 Integration of Digital Technology	Business digitization and eCommerce
5 Digital Public Services	eGovernment

Source: DG Connect

European Commission, Digital Scoreboard

Austria

In the DESI 2016, Austria is part of the running ahead cluster of countries: countries who score above the EU average and whose score grew faster than that of the EU as a whole (in comparison to the DESI 2015). Austria ranks 12th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 81% of Austrians aged 16-74 using the Internet and 37% being eGovernment users.

Belgium

In DESI 2016, Belgium performs better than the EU average but it has improved at a slower rate than the EU as a whole, which places it in the lagging ahead cluster of countries. However, compared with the previous year, Belgium has still improved or maintained its good position in all DESI dimensions. Belgium ranks fifth out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with an important share of regular Internet users (83%) while the eGovernment users appeared to be the 39% of the population.

Bulgaria

Bulgaria falls into the falling behind cluster of countries that score below the EU average and grew slower than the EU as a whole since last year. Bulgaria ranks 27th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with only 55% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 15% being eGovernment users.

Croatia

Croatia is part of the catching up cluster of countries: although it still performs below EU average, it has progressed faster than average over the past year. Croatia ranks 24th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016, with 66% of Croatians aged 16-74 using the Internet and 21% being eGovernment users.

Cyprus

In the DESI 2016, Cyprus is part of the falling behind cluster of countries: its score is lower than the EU average and over the last year it grew at a slower pace than the rest of the EU. Cyprus ranks 23rd out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 70% of Cypriots aged 16-74 using the Internet and 24% being eGovernment users.

Czech Republic

The Czech Republic is part of the falling behind cluster of countries because its DESI score is below the EU average and grew slower than that of the EU over the last year. The Czech Republic ranks 17th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016, with 77% of the people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 12% being eGovernment users.

Denmark

Denmark is part of the lagging ahead cluster of countries because it performs better than the EU average but has improved at a slower rate than the EU as a whole. Denmark ranks first out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016, with 93% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 71% being eGovernment users.

Estonia

In the DESI 2016, Estonia falls into the cluster of running ahead countries, scoring above the EU average and with rapid growth from last year. Estonia ranks 7th out of the 28 Member States in DESI 2016 with 86% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 80% being eGovernment users.

Finland

In the DESI 2016, Finland belongs to the cluster of countries with high scores but slow improvements called lagging ahead. Finland ranks 4th out of the 28 EU Member States with 91% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 63% being eGovernment users.

France

In DESI 2016, France falls into the cluster of falling behind countries, where it performs above average. France ranks 16th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016, with 81% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 48% being eGovernment users.

Germany

Germany is part of the running ahead cluster of countries because its DESI score is above the EU average and the country developed faster than the EU average over the last year. Germany ranks 9th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016, with 84% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 19% being eGovernment users.

Greece

Greece is part of the falling behind cluster of countries: its score is lower than the EU average and over the last year it grew at a slower pace than the EU. Greece ranks 26th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016, with 63% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 37% being eGovernment users.

Hungary

Hungary's score was lower than the EU average, and over the last year the overall score grew at a slightly slower pace than the EU. As such, Hungary is part of the falling behind cluster of countries. Hungary ranks 20th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 72% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 32% being eGovernment users.

Ireland

Ireland is in the lagging ahead cluster of countries, performing better than the EU average but improving at a slower rate than the EU as a whole. Ireland ranks 8th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 78% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 56% being eGovernment users.

Italy

Italy is part of the catching up cluster of countries: although it still performs below EU average, it has progressed faster than average over the last year. Italy ranks 25th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 63% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 18% being eGovernment users.

Latvia

Latvia falls into the cluster of catching up countries, scoring below the EU average but with an average growth above previous years. Latvia ranks 19th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 75% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 36% being eGovernment users.

Lithuania

Lithuania is part of the lagging ahead cluster of countries, because its DESI score is above the EU average but overall the country has developed slower than the EU over the last year. Lithuania ranks 13th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 69% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 42% being eGovernment users.

Luxembourg

Luxembourg’s scores places it among lagging ahead countries, who score above the EU average but whose score grew slower than that of the EU as a whole, in comparison with the DESI 2015. Luxembourg ranks 10th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 97% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 36% being eGovernment users.

Malta

Malta’s DESI 2016 score is above the EU average and the country developed faster than the EU over the last year, which places it in the running ahead cluster of countries. Malta ranks 11th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 74% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 28% being eGovernment users.

TheNetherlands

The Netherlands' DESI 2016 score is above the EU average and has developed faster than the EU over the last year, which places it in the running ahead cluster of countries. The Netherlands ranks 2nd out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 91% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 56% being eGovernment users.

Poland

Poland belongs to the falling behind cluster meaning that Poland’s performance is below the EU average and improved slower than EU as a whole. Poland ranks 22nd out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 65% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 22% being eGovernment users.

Portugal

Portugal is part of the running ahead cluster of countries because its DESI score is above the EU average and overall the country has developed faster than the EU over the last year. Portugal ranks 14th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 65% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 41% being eGovernment users.

Romania

Romania is part of the catching up cluster of countries: although it has performed below EU average, it has progressed faster than average over the last year. Romania ranks 28th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 52% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 8% being eGovernment users.

Slovakia

Slovakia is part of the falling behind cluster of countries: it performs below EU average, and overall the country has developed at a slower pace than the EU. Slovakia ranks 21st out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 74% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 16% being eGovernment users.

Slovenia

Slovenia is part of the catching up countries cluster: countries who score below the EU average but whose score grew faster than that of the EU as a whole compared with 2015. Slovenia ranks 18 out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 71% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 24% being eGovernment users.

Spain

Spain is part of the catching up cluster of countries because, although it still performs slightly below the EU as a whole, it has developed fast over the last year and got closer to the EU average. Spain ranks 15th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 75% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 38% being eGovernment users.

Sweden

Sweden recorded a high performance on all of the criteria and falls into the cluster of lagging ahead countries. Scoring well above the EU average but with below average growth from the previous year. Sweden ranks third in the EU regarding digitisation, according to DESI 2016, with 89% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 49% being eGovernment users.

United Kingdom

The United Kingdom is in the lagging ahead cluster of countries; performing better than the EU average but improving at a slower rate than the EU as a whole. The United Kingdom ranks 6th out of the 28 EU Member States in DESI 2016 with 90% of people aged 16-74 using the Internet and 34% being eGovernment users.

6. RECAP PRODUCT SELF-ASSESSMENT

Self-assessment is a natural first step on the process of improving a product regarding project management, results, action planning and implementation of change. This method provides a significant tool to avoid optimism bias when planning next steps. Self-assessment offers a unique insight into the most effective use of project management, as well as added value to the product and improves expected results.

To this end some serious considerations have to be taken into account in a “virtual” early self-assessment of the RECAP product service. These vary a lot and refer to natural, technical and human conditions. Namely, at this stage we may consider the following:

- On the spot checks require mostly very high resolution images
- Fast delivery of images is essential but not always feasible
- Cloud-free time series may be impossible
- Some people may be averse to work like this, in front of a desktop, a laptop or tablet loading documents, checking photos etc.
- Different quality of images may occur
- Land geometry differences is common
- There is low availability of images for all countries and regions
- It happens VHR images to require intensive pre-processing or processing
- Timeliness of data information may be encountered
- There are cases where spectral resolution is more important than spatial resolution for crop classification
- Soil data is difficult to collect from fields with thick canopy
- Why purchase a product that only covers cross - compliance rules?
- Many requirements cannot be controlled remotely (i.e. permits, storage) that means one cannot avoid on site visits
- Cross-compliance minimum requirements can be defined at national or regional level, therefore RECAP platform needs to set a variety of standards per country or region
- How much will it cost and can they paying agencies afford it? Is it possible to charge a different fee per country? Will charges be for setting up the platform – feeding the platform with data or updates – numbers of users?
- Some paying agencies develop their own e-services. Is it applicable to all e-platforms used by paying agencies? If not is it costly to adjust?
- If cost is high and an open public procurement needs to be followed, is it possible for a competitor to come up with a similar product and win the contract?

7. REGARDING THE COMPLETION OF THE DELIVERABLE

The identification of future potential competitors and a field research to be conducted to one of the upcoming regular meetings of the paying agencies is planned for the next period. It is expected that the completion of the deliverable with these two additional chapters will take place in May 2017, as there is an estimate for a paying agencies' summit taking place at some time during spring.

The aforementioned completion will allow a comprehensive set of conclusions based on the information of the document at hand plus the additional content on future potential competitors and paying agencies' views regarding the RECAP product.

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